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CLIMATE RESILIENT AND ENVIRONMENTALLY
SUSTAINABLE TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE,
WITH A FOCUS ON INLAND WATERWAYS

Deliverable 4.3: Development of the business models

**CRISTAL - Climate resilient and environmentally sustainable transport
infrastructure, with a focus on inland waterways**

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation/Term	Description
SCBA	Social Cost-Benefit Analysis
DT	Digital Twin
FOS	Fibre Optic System
IBS	Smart Buoys System
SCMS	Synchromodal Corridor Management System
EuRIS	European River Information System
LL	Living Labs
WP	Work Package
BMC	Business Model CANVAS
SIR	Subsurface Radar Inspection
FOS	Fibre Optic Sensors
AES	Acoustic Emission Sensors
API	Application Programming Interface

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1. Executive Summary

The main principles of this deliverable are:

- This deliverable is relevant for the success of the project because it supports the activation of the generic living lab approach in Task 4.4 of WP4.
- This deliverable contributes to Task 4.4 of WP4 where the SCBA and the BMC will be used to initiate and facilitate work on business models in the LL work. It contributes to the development of business models for the technologies developed in WP2, WP3 and WP5. It contributes as an input to the pilots (WP6, and then WP7-9) and the development of business models within those pilots. The deliverable contributes to the wider dissemination of the project in WP11 where it shall be disseminated and critiqued.
- The core collaborators who developed this deliverable were Thomas H Zunder, Cristian Ulianov (UNEW), Edwin van Hassel, and Emilia O'Neill (UnAnt). It was peer reviewed by Paola Bottega (Sogesca). Within each BMC workshop the relevant technology developers from WP2/3/5, the potential end users from WP6-9/11 and most of the partners in WP4 participated (see Table 2 on page 22)
- This report was developed from planning, desktop research, surveys, analysis, and workshops as detailed further below. The key events were the BMC workshops and SCBA surveys as follows:
 - Subsurface Inspection Radar, WP2, 29th August 2023.
 - Fibre Optic Sensors Technology, WP2, 26th September 2023.
 - Smart Buoys, WP2, 27th September 2023.
 - Acoustic Emissions System, WP2, 19th October 2023.
 - Digital Twins, WP5, 28th November 2023.
 - Synchromodal Corridor Management System, 4th December 2023.
 - Surveys during October and November 2023.
- The required information was gathered using presentations online in TEAMS, MIRO board BMC CANVAS in interactive workshops, and survey questionnaires.
- The information was analysed/developed using BMC Methodology detailed in Section 4 below, and SCBA Methodology detailed in 7 below.
- The beneficiaries are the technology developers, the pilots, potential actors and stakeholders, and the broader industry and academic communities.

1.1 Introduction

A summary of the main results achieved, and conclusions of the deliverable is:

The business model canvas is a step towards the concept of a business ecosystem for incorporating innovations (Moore, 1993) and strengthening their market position. The work in WP4.3 has started to bring synergies of the different actors and stakeholders together towards a common innovation and shared benefit. However, this Phase 4 Design process has just started, and as described in the Objectives and Figure 4 on page 15 below, the design of the BMC needs to now be validated by a Joint Workshop and then continued in WP4.4 in the Living Labs. There are noticeable absences of cost and revenue in most of the BMCs. The delineation between the customer segments is blurred and ambiguous. For the BMC to move to Phase 4 Implementation in WPs 6-9, further syncretic and standardised versions will be needed. This work will be done in WP4.4, however, the underlying technical capability of the innovations needs further examination in WP2, WP3 and WP5.

A BMC process should review the degree to which actors and stakeholders are key, and the nature of those stakeholders, actors or stakeholders as discussed in Section 3.2 below on page 13. We have done this for each BMC and found that not only are the actors and stakeholders different per technology, but that they

vary in the degree to which they are direct or indirect customers of the technology or solution. A similar analysis of key partners on the supply side shows similar variance. In most but not all BMC there is a symbiotic relationship with the infrastructure managers in that they appear as key partners enabling the BMC to function but also as customers; in practice this may disappear in a more developed business model where the information and data flows are processed by a DT or the SCMS as a service.

For evaluation and validation can proceed in WP10, T10.2 shall raise a series of open questions for the BMCs. The ability of the technical and pilot WPs to meet those open questions will form the evaluation in 10.2, with a repeated SCBA.

In this deliverable, the overall costs and benefits of the SCMS for the users and the developers are determined. The SCMS is the development in the CRISTAL project that targets the supply chain function of the inland waterway network (shippers, barge operators, etc.) while it also includes the different CRISTAL innovations which the FOS, AES, SB, SIR, and DTs.

All of these innovations have in common that they could contribute to a reduction in waiting time, and the improvement of the reliability of inland waterway transport, which should lead to a positive effect on the modal shift and a reduction in external costs. From the first results, it can be concluded that the SCMS demonstrates net benefits (135.225 € after a period of 20 years). The main benefits are obtained in risk mitigation, improved reliability, reduced waiting times, and improved sustainability. The obtained net benefits are also very sensitive to the transport volume in the corridor.

It also needs to be mentioned that some of the parameters are based on estimations (such as the cargo flow data) and preliminary results of the cost of the different technologies. In a later stage of the project, the data can be refined (also per region) and updated (in WP10).

The work reported in this deliverable met the objectives of Task 4.3 in the CRISTAL project effectively and provided liaison and co-creation of business models and associated SCBA for all technology providers in WPs 2/3/5 and in most cases drew the partners attention to ongoing operational and commercial opportunities. It has provided Task 4.4 of the project an extensive set of BMC, still formative and in development, that can be further elaborated and developed in the LL and in the pilots. It has provided the basis for evaluation in Task 10.2 and will form part of the dissemination and also evaluation of the project in WP10 and WP11.

1.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

The deliverable is structured to follow the revised flow of WP4, as described in section 2 below.

- ✓ Section 2 covers Revisions and scoping,
- ✓ Section 3 details Business Model Frameworks from a literature review,
- ✓ Section 4 explains the Business Model CANVAS methodology.
- ✓ The Development of business models for the CRISTAL technologies is reported in Section 5
- ✓ The Development of business models for the CRISTAL Digital Twins and SCMS in Section 6.
- ✓ Section 7 covers the Quantification method for potential benefits and cost for the CRISTAL solutions
- ✓ The Conclusions are reported in Section 8.

2. Revisions and scoping

2.1 Revised task flow

On reflection, we decided that the flow of WP4.3 should be amended so that T4.3.1 followed T4.3.2 and T4.3.3. This would enable the workshop-based 'bottom-up' CANVAS work to inform the quantitative modelling of T4.3.1. For this to work well, T4.3.1 task leader UnAnt provided a basic set of metrics that would need to be addressed (albeit at a broad-brush level) in the CANVAS work of T4.3.2 and T4.3.3.

Figure 1: Revised task flow for WP4

2.2 Scoping

To quantify the main cost and benefits of the potential implementation of the developed technologies in WP2 and the corridor management system (WP3).

- To develop business models for the developed technologies in WP2.
- To develop a holistic business model for the corridor management plan (WP3) including digital twins (WP5).

This report will be presented in 2024 at a Joint Workshop with the Advisory Board, pilot partners and Stakeholders to validate the developed business models.

T4.3.2 Four technology BMC workshops

It was decided that T4.3.2 would, as described in the DOA, address the four technologies defined in WP2 as separate CANVAS workshops and outputs.

- Fiber Optic Sensors Technology
- Smart Buoys
- Acoustic Emission System
- Subsurface Inspection Radar

T4.3.3 Digital Twin and SCMS BMC Workshops

It was decided that T4.3.3 should address the business model for the synchromodal corridor management system (SCMS) [WP3] including the digital twins (DTs) from [WP5], informed by the individual CANVAS outputs from T4.3.2. It was then agreed that there was value in a two-stage process: first the digital twins and then the full system with the SCMS.

T4.3.1 Cost Modelling for Business Models

We agreed as a team that the cost modelling work would be best started after T4.3.2 and parallel to T4.3.2 so that insights from the BMC workshops would inform the quantitative work.

2.3 Allocation of Resources

Resources were allocated at a top level as follows:

- T.4.3.1: UnAnt, UnGda
- T.4.3.2: UNEW, FRAUN (both), UnAnt, KTI, ENEA, EUMO
 - Plus ad hoc partners from WP2+ that have direct relationships to the technology, customers, or overall project.
- T.4.3.3: UNEW, CERTH, UnAnt, KTI, AIPO, UNITRA
 - Plus ad hoc partners from WP2+ that have direct relationships to the technology, customers, or overall project.

3. Business Model Frameworks

3.1 Definitions and Key Concepts

A *business model* is defined simply as the plan (and realization of that plan) of “how a firm makes money”. However, both academic research and practitioners have gone much beyond this simplistic definition of business models.

Business, management, and economics literature contains multiple business model definitions in abundance (Baden-Fuller & Morgan, 2010; Zott et al., 2011). In parallel, both operations management and ICT domains have a keen interest in business models, especially where they intersect with goods and service delivery (Zolnowski et al., 2014; De Marco et al., 2017; Carnaby et al., 2015; Ritter & Pedersen, 2020; Sjodin et al., 2020). In the following list, some definitions of business model are reported:

- “An abstract representation of an organization, be it conceptual, textual, and/or graphical, of all core interrelated architectural, co-operational, and financial arrangements designed and developed by an organization presently and in the future, as well all core products and/or technologies the organization offers, or will offer, based on these arrangements that are needed to achieve its goals and objectives” (Al-Debei & Avison, 2010)
- “Business model is a method of doing business, by which a company sustains itself and generates value” (Chesbrough & Rosenbloom, 2002)
- Osterwalder & Pigneur (2010) have stated: “a business model describes the rationale of how an organization creates, delivers, and captures value”.

It has been said, “that value proposition, value architecture, value finance, and value network articulate the primary constructs or dimensions of business models” (Al-Debei & Avison, 2010). A business model can be defined as a construct and also as a semantic model. Osterwalder’s and Pigneur’s (2010) ontology [structure] of a business model is called the *business model canvas (BMC)*. It shows the different elements of the business model with which an organisation can generate and deliver value and then capture reward for the same. It is important to note that, whilst Porter (1985) focused on the ‘firm’ in his seminal work on value chains, the BMC understands that a canvas may cover multiple firms acting as an organisation, but that ‘value’ can also be understood as non-financial. The canvas allows the design of different types of business models by splitting the critical questions into separate issues that build up the ontological structure.

The generation of value is the crucial element. Unless somebody finds value in the ‘offer’ of a product or service, then it will not be used and certainly not paid for. It is a value that makes the service or product *worth* something. The BMC’s key partners, key activities and channels by and large define the *value chain* that is needed to create value, as well as providing in reverse the supply chain that will deliver that value to the customer(s). Customer segments, channels and value propositions are part of the marketing management functions of any firm or organization. Managing costs and resources are part of production management functions. Revenue management falls between financial and marketing management functions.

In the CRISTAL technology context, the business model canvas is useful in many ways. It provides a tool with which the technologies can be designed in a way that the needed value chains can be constructed and pricing and revenue logic can be assessed. It can help identify key partners and activities needed to build up CRISTAL technologies. For example, public authorities and physical infrastructure providers belong to the actors that are needed to realize CRISTAL technologies, but there will be more specific to each BMC. The value propositions in the CRISTAL technology context not only include revenues in monetary terms. The value

includes also socio-economic-environmental impacts, such as safety and reduction in emissions and energy consumption. Therefore, the puzzle of the canvas becomes more complex and demanding.

We adopted the definition from Osterwalder & Pigneur (2010) which stated: “a business model describes the rationale of how an organisation creates, delivers, and captures value.”

Figure 2: Business Model Canvas for generic business model development (Strategyzer, 2018).

The BMC, shown in Figure 2 above contains nine building blocks – the different elements that could be used to define a proposed operation and value configuration. A BMC shows the demand side on the right: customer segments, relationships, and channels, and the supply side on the left: key partners, activities, and resources. The revenue streams generated from the business are found in the bottom right, with the cost structure to the bottom left. The value proposition - the accrued goods, technologies, services, and benefits - sits in the centre, being the meeting point of the ongoing transaction between supply and demand.

Developing a BMC requires a collaborative stakeholders’ workshop, at which those with an interest, mandate, and resources to plan a new sustainable business organization, can help populate the BMC with an eye to people, the planet, and profit.

The instructions on how to fill in each BMC section follow:

- Key partners
 - Identify who are the key partners in each pilot, what is their aim and what is their role.
- Key activities

- Identify the key activities that are needed to deliver the measure/solution.
- Key resources
 - Identify the resources needed to “produce” the measure/solution.
- Cost structure
 - Identify the cost categories (give figures if known).
- Value proposition
 - Identify what is the value proposition/added value that is being offered by this measure/solution.
- Customer relationships
 - Identify the type of relationship that is being used.
- Customer segments
 - Identify the customer segment that is being addressed with this measure/solution.
- Channels
 - Identify how we are reaching the customer in terms of communication channels.
- Revenue streams
 - Identify the revenues to be achieved.

The business model canvas is a step towards the concept of a *business ecosystem*. Business ecosystems work to incorporate innovations (Moore, 1993) and strengthen their market position by bringing synergies of different companies and public actors together towards a common innovation and shared benefit. The common grounding of an ecosystem is the shared fate of the involved actors (market players, customers, regulators) and the need to understand an organization’s role in the ecosystem (Iansiti & Levien, 2004).

Business models are revenue-generating logical structures, where the supplier receives money and customers receive benefits. As we move from the core technologies in CRISTAL (WP2) and encompass the digital twins (DTs) (WP5) and the synchromodal corridor management system (SCMS) (WP3), we are moving increasingly from a physical product and/or service to data, information, knowledge, and forecasts. Data are in the case of the DTs and SCMS the core “product delivered to intermediate and end users. When consumed and used in the right way, this will improve safety, enhance the efficiency of operations, and increase the productivity of the inland waterway transport systems separately and as a whole supply chain. In addition, good data can indirectly allow operations that cut the harmful effects of transport, such as emissions and road traffic. In other words, CRISTAL data, information, knowledge, and forecasts create value.

There are two different angles relevant to information value: the perceived value and the realized value (Ahituv, 1989). Typically, the first is associated with design and decision-making (we think and anticipate the value to be realized), whereas the latter is an empirical observation (we have witnessed how the value has been realized). Perceived value is hence always speculative in nature, while the realistic value is empirical and observable as described in Figure 3 (Leviakangas & Hautala, 2009; Hautala et al., 2011). This is particularly important to notice when thinking of the deployment of new technological solutions in transport, when the empirical experiences are often limited, both in terms of scope and time.

Figure 3: Perceived and realized value (Leviakangas & Hautala, 2009; Ahituv, 1989) after (Ahituv, 1989)

“The outcomes, i.e. the impacts, of information on the decisions and actions of users are mostly uncertain or at least stochastic: the impacts do not always manifest in exactly the same ways, and different users react differently, even in identical situations with the same information” (Hautala et al., 2011).

3.2 Stakeholder Perspectives on Business Models

Definitions and Key Concepts

The Merriam-Webster (2018) web-dictionary¹ gives three definitions of a *stakeholder*:

- “A person entrusted with stakes of bettors.”
- “One that has a stake in an enterprise.”
- “One who is involved in or affected by a course of action.”

It is easy to see that the last definition applies to CRISTAL technology deployment context – or in fact in any systemic context where a large number of actors are affected by an investment, decision, or action.

Stakeholder theory is an important concept. Introduced by Edward Freeman (2010) the theory states that business ethics and moral values play an important role in the management of business. The idea is not just to make money, but to satisfy the needs and aspirations of a larger group of actors, the stakeholders. This theory confronts the traditional view of utilitarian agent theory, where the idea of a firm is only to make money for shareholders. Since its introduction, it has spread widely and is one of the dominant paradigms of modern business theories.

Despite the apparent technical nature of CRISTAL technologies, it can be argued that they comply with stakeholder theory. Successful CRISTAL technology deployment will require multiple commitments of differing stakeholders, often with some conflicting interests that need to be accommodated. There is a substantial socio-economic ‘public good’ justification for CRISTAL technology that may make this context a fruitful application ground for stakeholder theory.

On the other hand, many of the actors in the inland waterways domain can make decisions on a utilitarian ‘bottom line’.

An *actor* is someone who has a role to play in the form of action, be that an investment or an operational activity. Stakeholders always include all actors, but not necessarily vice versa. Sometimes a stakeholder may not be an active party but still is affected e.g. by the externalities created by a system, e.g. a CRISTAL technology. The CRISTAL BMC process should identify the main actors that are needed for to successful commercialisation of CRISTAL technologies.

A BMC process can review the degree to which actors and stakeholders are key. Whilst a definitive list will be unique and specific to each business model, we can speculate that the following actors are likely to be involved (not exclusively):

- Infrastructure managers
- Public authorities (state, regional, city/local)
- Service providers
- Information system providers
- Vessel manufacturers
- Technology developers.

However, there are many other stakeholders that are either a part of the CRISTAL technologies deployment or affected by it, such as (not exclusively):

- Final end users
- Public transport operators
- Logistics service providers
- Road infrastructure managers
- Rail infrastructure managers
- Road/rail/sea transport operators.

This should be evaluated and reported at the end of the process.

Some of the stakeholders are motivated by business potential, some are motivated by the opportunity to provide better public service and create more sustainable mobility systems. In this sense, these stakeholders have their ‘own’ business models they are trying to realise. The challenge in CRISTAL technology deployment is to bring these ‘business models’ into **congruence** so that on an aggregate level the benefits are maximised without making any stakeholder seriously worse off than before. Using the value chain and value network models it is possible to identify both the actors and the stakeholders as well as to identify which type of motivations (benefits, costs, or impacts) these stakeholders might have about the particular CRISTAL technology service or service bundle.

Table 1: Stakeholder view added to a value chain, adapted from (Leviäkangas et al., 2019)

	Stakeholders					
		Actors				
Actor	Passive actor	Actor1	Actor2	Actor3	End-user	Affected Non-users
Function	raw data gathering	raw data purchase and distribution	data refining	distribution and service packaging	service consumption	Other system users
Benefit	Revenue from Actor1	Revenue from Actor2	Revenue from Actor3	Revenue from End-user	Private benefits from the service	Externalities
Cost	No direct additional cost	Payments for data	Payments to Actor1	Payments to Actor2	Payments to Actor3	

In this example, which is not specifically tailored to CRISTAL, Actors 1-3 and End-users are the active stakeholders, whereas the passive actor (raw data source) and other modes users have passive roles but yet are affected. The business model for the entire service is not sustainable if for example the raw data is not available or if non-users suffer from negative externalities. On the other hand, if there are significant positive externalities for the non-users, for example in terms of less congestion, there are possibilities for supplement revenues for Actors 1-3 with public-funded subsidies (Leviäkangas et al., 2019).

4. Business Model CANVAS methodology

The Business Model Canvas is a strategic management and lean start-up template for developing new or documenting existing, business models. It is a visual chart with elements describing the value proposition, infrastructure, customers, and finances of an existing or proposed business. It assists firms in aligning their activities, by illustrating potential trade-offs (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010).

The Canvas model starts with the single idea that the formal descriptions of the business become the building blocks for its activities. Osterwalder (2010) proposed a *single reference model* based on the similarities of a wide range of business model conceptualisations. With his *business model design template*, an enterprise can easily describe its business model.

4.1 Business Model Design Process

The business model design process adopted for the CRISTAL project considered five phases: Mobilize, Understand, Design, Implement, and Manage. These map onto the underlying structure of the project, not just during the project timeline but before in proposal and consortium mobilisation, and after in post-project impact exploitation.

Figure 4: Business Model Design Process, (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010)

The progression through these phases wasn't as linear as depicted in Figure 4 above. In particular, the Understanding and Design phases tended to proceed in parallel. Business model prototyping did start early in the Understanding phase, as partner VNF had prepared a first pass CANVAS within months of the project starting. Prototyping during the design phase may (still) lead to new ideas requiring additional research—and a revisiting of the Understand phase. Manage, the final phase is about continuously managing the business model(s). Considering the substantial investment an enterprise makes in producing a business model, it makes sense to extend its life through continuous management and evolution until it needs complete rethinking. Management of the model's evolution is an ongoing exploitation task, starting within the CRISTAL project but extending many years beyond. For each process phase, this report outlines the objective, the focus, and which activities in the CRISTAL programme of work support that phase.

Phase 1: Mobilize

Objective: Prepare for a successful business model design project

Focus: Setting the stage

Description: Assemble all the elements for a successful business model design. Create awareness of the need for a new business model, describe the motivation behind the project, and establish a common language to describe, design, analyse and discuss business models. This process began in the proposal writing when the members of the consortium came together and started to identify the need for new solutions, opportunities,

and the need for common understanding. It was then developed and written as a proposed process as WP4.3, which is where the work formally lies in the project. In addition, it has also been tentatively addressed in the technology development in WP2.

Phase 2: Understand

Objective: Research and analyse elements needed for the business model design effort

Focus: Immersion

Description: The technology developers (WP2, WP3 and WP5), and the stakeholders (WP4, also WP11 and the Living Labs) immersed themselves in relevant knowledge. We had numerous meetings and then workshops to understand business models and the BMC process. We then began each BMC session with presentations on customers, technology, and the business environment. We identified potential customers and their needs and problems.

Phase 3: Design

Objective: Generate and test viable business model options, and select the best

Focus: Inquiry

Description: Transform the information and ideas from the previous phase into business model prototypes that can be explored and tested. After an intensive business model inquiry, and a cost-benefit analysis, in T4.3.2 and T4.3.3 12, we co-designed BMC CANVAS and prepared this report as a business model input for the Living Lab work in T4.4. We expect there a further development of business models in T4.4, in the pilots WPs6-9, and then supported by exploitation and dissemination in WP11.

Phase 4: Implement

Objective: Implement the business model prototype in the field

Focus: Execution

Description: Implement the selected business model design. We expect the development of business models in the pilots of WP6-9, to be informed by this work and also the work in the Living Lab workshops of T4.4.

Phase 5: Manage

Objective: Adapt and modify the business model in response to market reaction

Focus: Evolution

Description: Set up the management structures to continuously monitor, evaluate, and adapt or transform the business model. It is expected that this will begin iteratively in the pilots of WP6-9 and then beyond the life of the project, with final plans being laid down in the final project Exploitation Plan. There will also be management and feedback on the business models in T10.2 which will evaluate the validity and the progress towards the BMC. This will lead to suggestions for evolution and change.

4.2 The Key Elements of the BMC

A BMC has nine parts as follows. In a sequenced fashion in a workshop, they are filled in using Post-it notes or the online equivalent. The sequence is often demand to offer to supply, or in our case, offer to demand to supply; followed then by finances.

Figure 5: Business Model Canvas Conceptualisation (numbering refers to sections below), (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010)

Offering

- Value Propositions (2): The collection of products and services a business offers to meet the needs of its customers. According to Osterwalder (2004), a company's value proposition is what distinguishes it from its competitors. The value proposition provides value through various elements, such as newness, performance, customisation, "getting the job done", design, brand/status, price, cost reduction, risk reduction, accessibility, and convenience/usability. The value propositions may be:
 - Quantitative- price and efficiency
 - Qualitative- overall customer experience and outcome

Customers

- Customer Segments (1): To build an effective business model, a company must identify which customers it tries to serve. Various sets of customers can be segmented, based on different needs and attributes, to ensure appropriate implementation of corporate strategy meets the characteristics of selected groups of clients. The different types of customer segments include:
 - Mass Market: The company applies additional segmentation within existing customer segments. In the segmented situation, the business may further distinguish its clients based on gender, age, and/or income etc.
 - Diversified: A business serves multiple customer segments with different needs and characteristics.

- Multi-Sided Platform / Market: For a smooth day-to-day business operation, some companies will serve mutually dependent customer segments. For example, a credit card company will provide services to credit card holders, while simultaneously assisting merchants who accept those credit cards.
- Channels (3): A company can deliver its value proposition to its targeted customers through different channels. Effective channels will distribute a company's value proposition in ways that are fast, efficient, and cost-effective. An organisation can reach its clients either through its own channels (store front), partner channels (major distributors), or a combination of both.
- Customer Relationships (4): To ensure its survival and success, any business, must identify the type of relationship it wants to create with its customer segments. Various forms of customer relationships include:
 - Personal Assistance: Assistance in the form of employee-customer interaction. Such assistance is performed either during sales, after-sales, and/or both.
 - Dedicated Personal Assistance: The most intimate and hands-on personal assistance, where a sales representative is assigned to handle all the needs and questions of a special set of clients.
 - Self-Service: The type of relationship that translates from the indirect interaction between the company and the clients. Here, an organisation provides the tools needed for the customers to serve themselves easily and effectively.
 - Automated Services: A system similar to self-service, but more personalised, as it can identify individual customers and his/her preferences.
 - Communities: Creating a community allows for direct interaction among different clients and the company. The community platform produces a scenario where knowledge can be shared, and problems are solved between different clients.
 - Co-creation: A personal relationship is created through the customer's direct input into the outcome of the company's products/services.

Infrastructure

- Key Activities (7): The most important activities in executing a company's value proposition.
- Key Resources (6): The resources that are necessary to create value for the customer. They are considered an asset to a company, which are needed to sustain and support the business. These resources could be human, financial, physical, and intellectual.
- Partner Network (8): To optimise operations and reduce the risks of a business model, an organisation usually cultivates buyer-supplier relationships so they can focus on their core activity. Complementary business alliances also can be considered through joint ventures and strategic alliances between competitors or non-competitors.

Finances

- Revenue Streams (5): the way a company makes income from each customer segment. There are several ways to generate a revenue stream:
 - Asset Sale: (the most common type) selling ownership rights to a physical product.
 - Usage Fee: money generated from the use of a particular service.
 - Subscription Fees: revenue generated by selling a continuous service.
 - Lending/Leasing/Renting: giving the exclusive right to an asset for a particular period of time.
 - Licensing: revenue generated from charging for the use of a protected intellectual property.

- Brokerage Fees: revenue generated from an intermediate service between 2 parties.
- Advertising: revenue generated from charging fees for product advertising.
- Cost Structure (9): This describes the most important monetary consequences of operating under different business models.
 - Classes of Business Structures:
 - Cost-Driven: focuses on minimising all costs – “no frills”.
 - Value-Driven: less concerned with cost; focuses on creating value for products and services.
 - Characteristics of Cost Structures:
 - Fixed Costs - costs are unchanged across different applications.
 - Variable Costs - these costs vary depending on the amount of production of goods or services.
 - Economies of Scale - costs go down as the amount of goods ordered or produced rises.
 - Economies of Scope - costs go down due to incorporating other businesses with a direct relation to the original product.

Sequencing and Presentation Notes

When co-creating a BMC, it is usual to begin either with the demand side and then the offer, or if an offer has already been scoped or partially developed, the offer and then the demand side. Given that the CRISTAL project was a response to an expressed demand in a call, elaborated further by customers inside the consortium, and technology has been developed based on that first pass, in all workshops we followed the sequence of:

1. Offer
2. Customer segments
 - a. Customer relationships
 - b. Channels
3. Key partners
 - a. Key Activities
 - b. Key resources
4. Revenue
5. Cost Structure

Note that in practice the process is iterative, as people react to, edit, comment on, and move between the nine elements. We observed this in all workshops.

Summary of Canvas

This concludes a basic introduction to the Business Model CANVAS and how it was used in CRISTAL. The tool's great strength is in offering the possibility to analyse every single key component of a business, to review strengths and weaknesses and to improve. Although this section has looked at each specific building block, once completed the Canvas should be viewed as a whole. This is key to understanding how everything is tied together as a working business plan. Changes made in a business influence the rest of the business model. (Carnaby et al., 2015)

5. Development of business models for the CRISTAL technologies

The CRISTAL technologies, the digital twins and the synchromodal corridor management system are to be implemented at varying levels up to the upper TRL targets of the project. To do so, new business models need to be co-created. To develop these business models also the benefits and the cost of these solutions need to be quantified. The Business Model CANVAS methodology had been selected in the project proposal and Grant Agreement and was implemented using MIRO online software to support online workshops. These BMC are envisioning a future state of a business organisation that has operationalised and deployed solutions; these are in most cases beyond the scale of the demonstrations funded and actioned in the CRISTAL pilots.

Note that in each case we present the BMC whole, however, this is not readable on an A4 page and will be expanded and explored in detail as each section continues.

In the tables for the offer, we identify perceived and realisable value by entering 'Y' where we believe the BMC can deliver. In the tables of suggested customer segments and key partners, we identify them by entering 'actor' or 'stakeholder' and then 'direct' or 'indirect'. The definitions of these terms are explained in Section 3 above.

Figure 6: BUSINESS MODEL CANVAS SETUP ON MIRO.COM, Source (Strategyzer, 2018)

5.1 Input from WP2 and WP4.2

The work in WP4.3 was informed directly by:

- presentations by technology developers regarding the individual technologies (Digital Twins, Smart Buoys, Fibre Optic Sensors, etc.).
- the results of the Questionnaire WP4 Deliverable 4.2

5.2 Participants

The following participants were identified as stakeholders (actors and researchers) for the 4 workshops, as detailed below in Table 2.

Table 2: T4.3.2 Technology BMC Stakeholders

CANVAS Workshops 4.3.2	Fiber Optic Sensor Technology	emails	Smart Buoys	emails	Acoustic emission	emails	Sub surface Inspection radar	emails
Facilitators	Thomas H Zunder (UNEW)	tom.zunder@ncl.ac.uk						
	Cristian Ulianov (UNEW)	cristian.ulianov@newcastle.ac.uk						
Partners	UNITRA	zanetta@uniontrasporti.it						
	FRAUN	ralf.fiedler@cml.fraunhofer.de						
	UANT	edwin.vanhassel@uantwerpen.be						
	UANT	marie.cryns@uantwerpen.be						
	GDANSK	jakub.jankiewicz@ug.edu.pl						
	GDANSK	ernest.czermanski@ug.edu.pl						
Customers	AIPO (ask Luca to name and invite) <i>[maybe not needed for this]</i>	luca.crose@agenziapo.it	AIPO (ask Luca to name and invite) <i>[maybe not needed for this]</i>	luca.crose@agenziapo.it	AIPO (ask Luca to name and invite) <i>[maybe not needed for this]</i>	luca.crose@agenziapo.it	AIPO (ask Luca to name and invite) <i>[maybe not needed for this]</i>	luca.crose@agenziapo.it
	VNF (stephane offer choice)	stephane.gastarriet@vnf.fr						
	†-PIT (representing infra)	tomasz.markowski@pit.lukasiewicz.gov.pl						
	CERTH (as developer of corridor mgt system and customer of data flow)	ortsolakis@certh.gr	CERTH (as developer of corridor mgt system and customer of data flow)	ortsolakis@certh.gr	CERTH (as developer of corridor mgt system and customer of data flow)	ortsolakis@certh.gr	CERTH (as developer of corridor mgt system and customer of data flow)	ortsolakis@certh.gr
	FRAUN (as developer of digital and customer of data flow)	bjoern.kraemer@iml.fraunhofer.de	FRAUN (as developer of digital and customer of data flow)	bjoern.kraemer@iml.fraunhofer.de	FRAUN (as developer of digital and customer of data flow)	bjoern.kraemer@iml.fraunhofer.de	FRAUN (as developer of digital and customer of data flow)	bjoern.kraemer@iml.fraunhofer.de
Andrea Ballarin <> for Infrastrutture Venete (IV)	andrea@networkwins.it	Andrea Ballarin <> for Infrastrutture Venete (IV)	andrea@networkwins.it	Andrea Ballarin <> for Infrastrutture Venete (IV)	andrea@networkwins.it	Andrea Ballarin <> for Infrastrutture Venete (IV)	andrea@networkwins.it	
Developers	ENEA	sonia.giovinazzi@enea.it	PIT	tomasz.markowski@pit.lukasiewicz.gov.pl	CERTH	ortsolakis@certh.gr	UNEW	mark.robinson@ncl.ac.uk
		michele.caponero@enea.it						
		cristina.mazzotta@enea.it			CERTH (Theo)	ttsenis@certh.gr	EUMO	Simon.hartshorne@eurom

Following polls, the following dates were chosen for the online workshops.

Dates of CRISTAL WP4 T4.3.2 BMC Workshops

- Subsurface Inspection Radar, WP2, 29th August 2023
- Fibre Optic Sensors Technology, WP2, 26th September 2023
- Smart Buoys, WP2, 27th September 2023
- Acoustic Emissions System, WP2, 19th October 2023

Agenda for all workshops

- Overview of WP4.3, Purpose of the Workshop: (UNEW) 10 minutes
- Introductory video on BMC: 2 minutes
- Introduction to the relevant technology: (DEVELOPER) 15-25 minutes
- Co-creation of the BMC on MIRO by all participants with ad hoc conversation and discussion as needed.

Presentations

The technical presentations, which were to be composed of one-third of technology, one-third of use cases and one-third of customer benefits; are available on request to the project team.

The video explanation of CANVAS is on YouTube here: <https://youtu.be/QoAOzMTLP5s>

5.3 Subsurface Inspection Radar Business Model CANVAS

Subsurface Radar Inspection, WP2, 29th August 2023

Thomas McDonald of UNEW made a presentation of the technical, use case and user benefits of the Subsurface Inspection Radar technology developed in WP2, primarily by UNEW and EUMO in the French pilot (VNF). For the BMC it is worth noting the use cases and user benefits presented by Thomas with 3 of the slides presented, see Figure 7, Figure 8, and Figure 9 below.

2.0 Use Cases For Inland Waterways Maintenance

Potential Use-Cases

Identified Use-Case:	Scope:	Priority Estimate:
(1) SIR for Sidewall Inspection in Narrow/Wide Gauge Lock (different asset designs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Detection of potential critical damage (e.g., cracks, voids, ingress, corrosion, etc.) - Inspection window: 8-10 days. - Full scans vs localised scans? 	HIGH/MEDIUM <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Damages in sidewalls may cause critical failures. - Narrow locks are older. - Age induces fatigue.
(1.2) SIR for Sidewall Structure Mapping in Narrow Locks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Limited historical records. - Concrete reinforcements are unknown. - Assists future maintenance. 	MEDIUM <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Relatively few old locks. - Prioritise defect spotting?
(2) SIR for Subsurface Inspection of Dam Structures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Detection of potential critical damage (e.g., cracks, voids, ingress, corrosion, etc.) - Restricted by base water level. 	HIGH <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High likelihood of damages due to extreme loads and stresses. - Safety-critical structure.
(3) SIR for Inspection of Earthworks Adjacent to Lock Chamber Sidewalls	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Detection of potential damage (e.g., voids, water ingress, etc.) - GPR operation akin to use cases for similar applications. 	MEDIUM <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - R&I less challenging. - Impact of defects limited.
(4) SIR for Bottom/Bed of lock Chamber Inspection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Detection of potential critical damage (e.g., cracks, voids, ingress, corrosion, etc.) - Inspection window: 8-10 days. 	LOW <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Much lower likelihood of issues on bottom of locks. - Lower impact on critical engineering structures.

Figure 7: Use Cases for SIR

2.1 Use Cases For Inland Waterways Maintenance

Stakeholders

End-users	SIR outcomes and advantages	Prospective benefits
Direct: A. Infrastructure Managers B. Entities in charge of maintenance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Accurate & reliable detection of lock subsurface anomalies. - Defect type and size discrimination; this info may be further used by experts to determine <u>severity grading</u> (that may eventually feed into a general <u>asset health indicator</u>) - Intuitive data output format, content and faithfulness to surveyed topography → <u>easy end user hazard assessment</u>. - Modular design allows for <u>operation within drainage window</u>. - Low maintenance servicing. 	Enhanced Reliability, Availability, Maintainability and Safety (RAMS) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Periodic inspections would enable <u>preventive maintenance</u> of assets, reducing thus maintenance costs and improving the availability of locks by reducing their closure for maintenance. - Accurate record of information on asset condition would <u>prevent unexpected critical failures</u> that may impact on <u>availability of waterway, traffic, safety of operations, etc.</u>
Indirect: C. Operators		
Other Interested Parties E. Inland navigation authorities (local/national/etc.) F. Customers (logistic companies, passengers, etc.) G. Others (standards, policymakers, etc.)		

Example damage that requires subsurface scanning - Breached subsurface void releases retained water during lock drainage.

BMC Workshop, MS Teams, 29/08/2023

Figure 8: Use Cases for SIR, Stakeholders

Table 3: SIR Key Propositions and Benefits

Benefits	Perceived Value	Realisable Value
Avoid degradation	Y	Y
Knowledge of issues to address if/when a lock is emptied.	Y	Y
Incorporation in asset/business continuity management procedures and practices	Y	Y
Better infra manager reputation and relationship with stakeholders	Y	
Improved quality assurance for customers/regulators	Y	
Priority list for lock maintenance	Y	Y
A computerised maintenance management system (CMMS)	Y	Y
Non-invasive method, no drillings, no destruction of walls	Y	Y
Subsurface Lock Wall Inspection	Y	Y
Possibly lower cost than the invasive methods	Y	
Identify the problems before the infrastructure failure, probably giving time to intervene	Y	
Non-invasive technology	Y	Y
Informing predictive and preventative maintenance	Y	Y
Steel reinforcement detection	Y	Y
By providing informed information about the status of the infrastructure to better plan and maintain it.	Y	Y
Reduced non-operational time at locks	Y	
Certified approach compliant with EU standards, e.g. ISO 55000	Y	Y
More intuitive 3D models (than 'conventional' 2D radar graphs)	Y	Y
Fault Detection in lock walls	Y	Y
Increased inland navigation attractiveness, reduced CO2 emissions and pollution due to road traffic	Y	
Easier to operate	Y	Y
Void recognition	Y	Y
Informed maintenance better-planned lock possessions	Y	Y

The BMC assessed the customer segments as follows below in Table 4. We noted that most of these customers are direct actors able to directly purchase the offer, with a few indirect stakeholders who will benefit indirectly.

Table 4: SIR Customer Segments

Customer	Actor / Stakeholder	Direct / Indirect
VNF	A	D
Infra managers	A	D
Any authority operating locks	A	D
River Po Infra managers	A	D
Pleasure craft	S	I
Traffic/Customers navigating the locks	S	I
The Flemish waterway (DVW) Wallonia: voies-hydrauliques.wallonie.be Rijkswaterstaat (NL).	A	D
Logistics Providers	S	I
Barge operators	S	I
The (IWT) infrastructure provider	A	D
Construction companies	A	I
Infrastructure owners and the asset and operation management team	A	D
Maintenance Practitioners	A	D
Private inspection companies	A	D

To deliver the business model, the workshop identified key partners shown below in Table 5. Note that key partners can include both organisations inside and outside of CRISTAL and may even include some that are also customers where they have multiple roles in this domain. In this exercise, a clear separation emerged between those that felt that there were limited, or nil external partners needed to achieve the direct customer benefits, and those that saw the indirect benefits as enabled through integration with the Digital Twins and the SCMS.

Table 5: SIR Key partners

Key partners	Actor / Stakeholder	Direct / Indirect
Data providers/platform to train AI	S	I
AI developers	S	I
Technology providers and units do not have to be linked to anything else. Stand-alone service	A	D
The SMCS (+DTs)	S	I
Links with software providers to create a user-friendly interface	A	D
AI and machine learning specialists to provide auto recognition and identification of subsurface faults	S	I
Engineering consultancies	A	I
Civil construction and maintenance organisations	A	D
Robot builder	?	?
Universities	A	D

We can now look at the key activities and resources needed to create the offer. For this BMC they were as shown in Figure 11. The activities seem direct and actual, note the addition of the need for a BMC to convince the customer.

Figure 11: SIR Key activities and Resources

The customer relationships and channels are shown in Figure 12. Note that in one sense they are simple, a monthly contact and then on demand. However, there are also longer-term marketing or dissemination activities such as trade shows, journals, trade associations and European Technology Platforms (ETPs) and projects. Channels are both active (guides, direct contact) and responsive (public tenders).

The Cost Structure and Revenue boxes remind us that there is a minimum amount of money (resources) needed to develop a working prototype (EU/funding). After that, you can spend more money (resources) to further tailor/improve the product IF there is sufficient demand for the product.

The CANVAS details a fundamental two-part income stream: a one-time payment for the installation of the tech followed by a "monthly" subscription for providing the service.

This is all detailed in Figure 13 & Figure 14 below. Note that there are some additional ideas for revenue, such as the sale of algorithm, and indirect revenue from improved lock operation leading to a possible profit share with IWT infrastructure managers.

Figure 12: SIR Customer Relationships and Channels

Figure 13: SIR Cost Structure

Source: [Strategyzer AG](#) | License: [CC By-SA 3.0](#)

Figure 14: SIR Revenue Streams

5.4 Fibre Optic Sensors Technology Business Model CANVAS

Fibre Optic Sensors, WP2, 26th September 2023

ENEA made a presentation of the technical, use case and user benefits of the Fibre Optic Sensors technology developed in WP2, primarily by ENEA. For the BMC it is worth noting the use cases and user benefits presented with these 3 of the slides presented, see Figure 15, Figure 16, Figure 17 below.

FOS sensors towards smart navigability of free-flowing waterways (1/2)

Measure of Navigability nowadays

- ✓ only one measure daily via bathymetric survey via boat
- ✓ high environmental impact
- ✓ Might not be easy in critical situation

Daily Bulletin of navigability (bathymetry) in critical sections of the Po river

Smart Monitoring of Navigability

FOS sensors will allow

- **A continuous monitoring (all day long every day also in critical situation)**
- End-user will receive KPIs of navigability directly on smart dashboards
- Very low to zero environmental impacts in the operational phase

FOS are well suited for **permanent installation with continuous monitoring**

Figure 15: Use Cases for FOS

FOS sensors towards smart navigability of free-flowing waterways (2/2)

Smart Monitoring of Navigability through FOS sensors

Pads will be manufactured using materials for submarine applications, adopting standard design of pads for industrial scales

Pads will house the fiber optic enclosure for fusion splices (optical connection between sensors and filers)

Pads will be chained on a cable

Figure 16: Use Cases for FOS, Stakeholders

FOS sensors for informing navigability conditions in free-flowing waterway

- ❖ **Detecting sand dune formation in critical sections of the Po River** - by weighing pads sensitive to the dune weight

PROS (further to the ones in slide 8)

- Sensor embedded in the optical fiber, no power supply at the sensing location,
- Very stable response in the long term; mature technology for underwater operation (used in deep sea for oil/gas pipelines monitoring)
- Promising design for endurance to dredging machinery is technical feasible (large founded rugged base hosting and protecting a central active weighing pad; deep buried connection fiber optic cables)

Bottleneck

- **INSTALLATION Costs are not affordable within CRISTAL project budget**
 - **Estimated 250k euro for prototype production and installation**

•TRL of the sensors (TRL 4)

Figure 17: User Benefits for FOS

Suitably briefed with the technology context and use cases/benefits the attendees co-created a BMC as follows. The BMC is shown below in Figure 18.

The CRISTAL Fibre Optics Business Model Canvas

Source: Strategyzer AG | License: CC BY-SA 3.0

Figure 18: CRISTAL Fibre Optic Sensors Business Model CANVAS

The key propositions identified are summarised in Table 6 below, with an assessment of whether the value is perceived, and then if it is realisable within this business model. Note that a perceived value may be realised in collaboration with other technologies or business models, here we assess if the technology in this BMC will do that realisation. Much of the value generated by the FOS is realisable

from the technology and this associated business model, however, an important minority is perceived value that would need integration with a digital twin or similar for realisation.

Table 6: FOS KeyPropositionss and Benefits

Benefits	Perceived Value	Realisable Value
Timely and effective dragging operations more respective of the river ecosystem less impacts (and may be even cheaper)	Y	Y
Reliable transit times	Y	
Non-mobile hard point for dredging justifying a fixed fattening monitoring installation above the fibre	Y	Y
Reliable Volume estimation for dredgers to plan and effectively schedule their resources	Y	Y
Higher availability	Y	
Providing real-time information about the water level of the water --> will lead to better utilization of the barges on the waterway.	Y	Y
A service package " sensor and dredging" could be offered	Y	
Providing information to the waterway manager to do dedicated maintenance on the waterway.	Y	
Low to zero carbon footprint in the operational phase	Y	Y
Permanent continuous monitoring	Y	Y
Less manpower is required for surveying boats	Y	Y
Lower maintenance costs	Y	Y
Better planning basis for transport	Y	
Mitigation strategy to reduce impacts in flooding events?	Y	
More frequent and less environmentally disruptive maintenance [query?]	Y	Y

The BMC assessed the customer segments as follows in Table 7 below. We noted that most of these customers are direct actors able to directly purchase the offer, with stakeholders who will benefit indirectly.

Table 7: FOS Customer Segments

Customer	Actor / Stakeholder	Direct / Indirect
Associations that manage free-flowing waterways	A	D
Maintenance waterway manager	A	D
IWW infrastructure operators	A	D
Any (sea-) port authority	A	D
Barge operators, 3/4PLS, infra managers	S	I
Barge operators (who want to optimise the utilisation)	S	I
Civil protection (society)	S	D
Waterways Logistics Operators	A	I
Industrial companies like TKS or BASF (planning of the transports during low water periods)	S	I

In order to deliver the business model, the workshop identified key partners shown below in Table 8. Note that key partners can include both organisations inside and outside of CRISTAL and may even include some that are also customers where they have multiple roles in this domain. Noticeably many of these key partners are stakeholder and indirect, and if one were to be critical one might suggest that many of the associations might be indirect stakeholder customer segments and that the digital twins and SCMS are downstream customers of fibre optic sensors.

Table 8: FOS Key partners

Partner	Actor / Stakeholder	Direct / Indirect
Organizations working on digital twins and 3D modelling	S	D
University and researchers modelling dynamic movements of riverbeds	A	D
worth involving Environmental agencies such as ARPAE https://www.arpae.it/it and other bodies having a regulator role	S	I
AGiD (https://www.agid.gov.it/en) Agency for Digital Italy and UNI for related standards and standardised data models	S	I
Waterway infrastructure operators	A	D
hydraulic engineers	S	D
The digital twins & SCMS	S	D
AGiD (https://www.agid.gov.it/en) also for interoperability of this network of sensors with other networks already operating (e.g. networks of sensors operated by the National Civil Protection	S	I
Associations like CCNR (for regulations, and dissemination)	S	I

We can now look at the key activities and resources needed to create the offer. For this BMC they were as shown below in Figure 19 essentially functional, but with the key need for proofs of concepts in different regions and subsequent benchmarking using KPIs. That is Task 10.1 in the project.

Figure 19: FOS Key Activities and Resources

The customer relationships and channels are shown in Figure 20. Note that in one sense they are simple, data flows hourly and then face-to-face customer relationship management with on-demand interaction with dredgers.

The Cost Structure and Revenue boxes remind us that there is a minimum amount of money (resources) needed to develop a working prototype (EU/funding). After that, you can spend more money (resources) to further tailor/improve the product IF there is sufficient demand for the product.

The CANVAS details a fundamental two-part income stream: a one-time payment for the installation of the tech followed by a "monthly" subscription for providing the service.

This is all detailed in Figure 21 & Figure 22 below. Note that there are some additional ideas for revenue, such as co-funding and indirect revenue from improved lock operations leading to a possible profit share with IWT infrastructure managers.

This technology business model has a very clear cost structure understood in euros.

Figure 20: FOS Customer Relationships and Channels

Figure 21: FOS Cost Structure

Figure 22: FOS Revenue Streams

5.5 Smart Buoys Business Model CANVAS

Smart Buoys, WP2, 27th September 2023

Ł-PIT made a presentation of the technical, use case and user benefits of the Smart Buoys technology developed in WP2, primarily by Ł-PIT in the Polish pilot. A BMC prepared by Ł-PIT was then presented. Suitably briefed with the technology context and a BMC the attendees critiqued and commented. The BMC is shown below in Figure 23.

Figure 23: CRISTAL Smart Buoys Business Model CANVAS

The key propositions identified are summarised in Table 9 below, with an assessment of whether the value is perceived, and then if it is realisable within this business model. Note that a perceived value may be realised in collaboration with other technologies or business models, here we assess if the technology in this BMC will do that realisation. Much of the value generated by the Smart Buoys is realisable from the technology and this associated business model, however, an important minority is knowledge that is seen as perceived value but would need integration with a digital twin or similar for realisation.

Table 9: Smart Buoys Key Propositions and Benefits

Value Propositions	Perceived Value	Realisable Value
Knowledge of the state of the river environment in real time	Y	
Knowledge about shipping traffic (speed and direction of movement - start and destination of the course - for those who identify themselves + detection of unidentified units) - the possibility of using this knowledge for toll collection	Y	
The comprehensiveness of the solution	Y	Y
Standardized format for data transmission	Y	Y
Ease of access in one place reduces the time of planning organization and control of the transport process	Y	Y
Faster ability to respond to emergencies & anomalies	Y	
No need to invest in the maintenance of metering infrastructure	Y	Y
Facilitating the flow of information between participants of the WT process	Y	Y
Possibility to propose additional new services based on available data	Y	Y
Disaster prediction	Y	

The BMC assessed the customer segments as follows in Table 10. We noted that most of these customers are direct actors able to directly purchase the offer, with logistics operators who will benefit indirectly.

Table 10: Smart Buoys Customer Segments

Customer Segments	Actor / Stakeholder	Direct / Indirect
Infrastructure manager	A	D
Logistics operators	S	I
Owners of means of transport/Shipowners	A	I
Domain software companies	A	D

To deliver the business model, the BMC identified key partners shown below in Table 11. This model has a clear limited list of actors with direct control and one stakeholder supporting system promotion.

Table 11: Smart Buoys Key partners

Key Partners	Actor / Stakeholder	Direct / Indirect
Physical resource providers (buoys, sensors, etc.)	A	D
Polish Waters (as an org. issuing consents)	A	D
IMGW (Institute of Meteorology and Water Economy)	A	D
Certification body	A	D
Industry organizations supporting system promotions	S	I

We can now look at the key activities and resources needed to create the offer. For this BMC they were as shown below in Table 12 essentially functional and self-contained.

Table 12: Smart Buoys Key Activities and Resources

Key Actions
System design
Production in test version / Usability tests / Obtaining permits / Implementation
Market research (including consultations on the need for data and information in the IWT area / Selection of the final business model
Maintenance and development, including the organization of the technical department supporting the efficient operation of the system and the development of new functionalities
Key Resources
Physical resources: buoy, physical value sensors, power sources, servers, software
Human resources: IT and hardware team, mechanics
Funding: funding from the CRISTAL project
Intellectual Resources: Consulting on Data Needs and Information Flow
Information resources from IMGW, as a complement to the system

The customer relationships and channels are shown in Table 13. One relationship is simple: direct sales. The second is novel, a social utility using the information with a wider community. Lastly is the co-creation of top-level solutions (like a digital twin maybe) with domain software creators. Again, the channels are well segmented: sell it all to Polish Waters; sell the data; sell the data or maybe a service through a third party.

Table 13: Smart Buoys Customer Relationships and Channels

Customer Relationship
Direct account manager
Self-service on an online platform building a community around the solution - an information system for social utility
Co-creation of the solution with the client including cooperation with the creators of domain software)
Channels
Own channel - sale of the entire system to Polish Waters (transfer of all activities to the operator or service support) – direct sales/salesman
Own channel - i.e. L-PIT is the owner of the system and sells data - direct sales /salesman - sales platform
Partner channel - L-PIT uses sales support from an external company - direct sales/salesperson - sales platform

The Cost Structure and Revenue boxes remind us that there is a minimum amount of money (resources) needed to develop a working prototype (EU/funding). After that, you can spend more money (resources) to further tailor/improve the product IF there is sufficient demand for the product.

This is all detailed quite well but without specific costs in Table 14 below.

Table 14: Smart Buoys Cost Structure and Revenue Streams

Cost Structure
Fixed costs: maintenance of the enterprise, including back-office; costs related to access to river infrastructure; depreciation
Variable costs: costs related to the production and development of the system, maintenance costs of infrastructure server, data transmission costs; service technicians, subcontracting; consumption of materials and energy, cost of promotion, security costs, upgrade costs
Revenue Streams
Fee for the purchase of buoys / Leasing of the equipment / Fee for the lease of the device
System maintenance fee
Access to data on the platform

5.6 Acoustic Emission System Business Model CANVAS

Acoustic Emissions Sensors, WP2, 19th October 2023

CERTH made a presentation of the technical, use case and user benefits of the Acoustic Emissions System technology developed in WP2, primarily by CERTH for the Italian and French pilots. For the BMC it is worth noting the use cases and user benefits presented with 4 of the slides presented, see Figure 24, Figure 25, Figure 26 & Figure 27 below.

Figure 24: Italian Case Study for Acoustic Emissions Sensors

Figure 25: French Case Study for Acoustic Emissions Sensors, Stakeholders

Client Benefits Using AE on Water-locks

Using **Acoustic Emission (AE)** for structural health monitoring of water lock gates can offer several benefits to potential customers, and these customers can span various sectors. Here are some potential customers and the benefits they can derive from this technology:

Government Agencies and Waterway Authorities:
Benefits: Water lock gate monitoring through AE can help prevent costly infrastructure failures. This is especially critical for government agencies responsible for maintaining waterways, as it ensures smooth navigation, flood control, and efficient water resource management.

Commercial Shipping and Transportation Companies:
Benefits: Commercial entities involved in shipping and transportation depend on reliable waterways. Structural health monitoring of lock gates minimizes the risk of unexpected closures, delays, and damage to vessels, which can result in substantial cost savings.

Figure 26: Client Benefits for Acoustic Emissions Sensors

Client Benefits Using AE on Water-locks

Recreational Boaters and Tourism Operators:
Benefits: Recreational boaters and tourism operators benefit from AE-monitored lock gates by experiencing fewer disruptions in their waterway journeys. This can lead to improved customer satisfaction and more repeat business.

Local Communities:
Benefits: Communities located near waterways benefit from AE-monitored lock gates by avoiding the disruptions caused by unexpected closures or repairs. This can enhance the quality of life and the local economy.

Acoustic Emission Technology Providers:
Benefits: Companies specializing in AE technology can sell monitoring systems, sensors, and related services to organizations interested in structural health monitoring. This opens up new markets and revenue streams for these providers.

Figure 27: Client Benefits for Acoustic Emissions Sensors

Suitably briefed with the technology context and use cases/benefits the attendees co-created a BMC as follows. The BMC is shown in Figure 28 below.

CRISTAL Acoustic Emission Business Model CANVAS

Figure 28: CRISTAL Acoustic Emissions Sensors Business Model CANVAS

The key propositions identified are summarised in Table 15 below, with an assessment of whether the value is perceived, and then if it is realisable within this business model. Note that a perceived value may be realised in collaboration with other technologies or business models, here we assess if the technology in this BMC will do that realisation. Much of the value generated by the Acoustic Emissions Sensors is realisable from the technology and this associated business model.

Table 15: Acoustic Emissions Sensors Key Propositions and Benefits

Benefits	Perceived Value	Realisable Value
Justify that the defects detected can be reparable	Y	Y
Justify that the defects detected can prevent frequent breakdowns of door locks and equipment of door locks	Y	Y
Permanent continuous monitoring	Y	Y
Lower maintenance costs	Y	
To provide real-time monitoring of the health of the infrastructure	Y	Y
To better plan maintenance work	Y	
Less manpower is required for surveying locks	Y	Y
To reduce downtime of the critical infrastructure.	Y	Y

The BMC assessed the customer segments as shown below in Table 16. We noted that most of these customers are direct actors able to directly purchase the offer, with stakeholders who will benefit indirectly. The CRISTAL Digital Twins is identified clearly as a customer for this business model, note it is also identified as a key partner later.

Table 16: Acoustic Emissions Sensors Customer Segments

Customer	Actor / Stakeholder	Direct / Indirect
The maintenance staff of the infra manager	A	D
Waterways Logistics Operators	S	I
IWT infrastructure manager	A	D
IWW infrastructure operators	A	D
digital twins WP5	A	D
Any (sea-) port authority	A	D
Civil protection (society)	S	I

In order to deliver the business model, the workshop identified key partners shown below in Table 17. Note that key partners can include both organisations inside and outside of CRISTAL and may even include some that are also customers where they have multiple roles in this domain. Noticeably all of

these key partners are actors and direct, this is a very focused BMC. Note that the technology developer views digital twins as both a key partner and a customer.

Table 17: Acoustic Emissions Sensors Key partners

Key partners	Actor / Stakeholder	Direct / Indirect
Equipment providers	A	D
Companies that can repair the defects before the defect become visible	A	D
CERTH as a technology developer	A	D
University and researchers	A	D
Maintenance department of IWT manager	A	D
Digital Twins	A	D

We can now look at the key activities and resources needed to create the offer. For this BMC they were as functional as shown in Figure 29, but with the key need for proofs of cost benefits through a CBA and subsequent benchmarking in case studies using KPIs - Task 10.1 in the project.

Figure 29: Acoustic Emissions Sensors Key Activities and Resources

Figure 30: FOS Customer Relationships and Channels

The customer relationships and channels are shown in Figure 30. This BMC views the relationship as traditional and then a data flow, perhaps daily or weekly in an ongoing business.

The Cost Structure and Revenue boxes remind us that there is a minimum amount of money (resources) needed to develop a working prototype (EU/funding). After that, you can spend more money (resources) to further tailor/improve the product IF there is sufficient demand for the product.

The CANVAS details a fundamental two-part income stream: a one-time payment for the installation of the tech followed by a "monthly" subscription for providing the service. This is a very underdeveloped part of the BMC.

This is all detailed in Figure 31 & Figure 32 below.

Figure 31: Acoustic Emissions Sensors Cost Structure

Figure 32: Acoustic Emissions Sensors Revenue Streams

6. Development of business models for the CRISTAL Digital Twins and SCMS

The CRISTAL digital twins and SCMS are to be implemented at varying levels up to the upper TRL targets of the project. To do so, new business models need to be co-created. To develop these business models the benefits and the cost of these solutions also need to be quantified. The Business Model CANVAS was implemented using MIRO online software to support online workshops. These BMC are envisioning a future state of a business organisation that has operationalised and deployed solutions; these are in most cases beyond the scale of the demonstrations funded and actioned in the CRISTAL pilots.

Note that in each case we present the BMC whole, however, this is not readable on an A4 page and will be expanded and explored in detail as each section continues.

In the tables for the offer, we identify perceived and realisable value by entering ‘Y’ where we believe the BMC can deliver. In the tables of suggested customer segments and key partners, we identify them by entering ‘actor’ or ‘stakeholder’ and then ‘direct’ or ‘indirect’. The definitions of these terms are explained in Section 3 above.

6.1 Input from WP2 and WP4.2

The work in T4.3.3 was informed directly by presentations by technology developers regarding the individual technologies (Digital Twins, Smart Buoys, Fibre Optic Sensors, etc.). The work in T4.3.3 was informed directly by the results of the Questionnaire WP4 Deliverable 4.2. The work in T4.3.3 was directly informed by the BMC developed in T4.3.2.

6.2 Participants

The following participants were identified as stakeholders (actors and researchers) for the two workshops, as detailed in Table 18 below.

Table 18: T4.3.3 digital twins & SCMS BMC Stakeholders

Orestis Tsolakis, CERTH	Tammo Märtens, Fraunhofer
Achim Klukas, FRAUNHOFER	Stephane Gastarriet, VNF
Sonia Giovinazzi, ENEA	Cristian Ulianov, UNEW
Ebrahim Ehsanfar, FRAUNHOFER	Ralf Fiedler , FRAUNHOFER
Norina Szander, , KTI	Björn Kramer, FRAUNHOFER
Theocharis Tsenis, CERTH	Paola Bottega, SOGESCA
Luca Zanetta, Union Trasporti	Marie Cryns, U Antwerpen
Tomasz Markowski, Łukasiewicz - PIT	Elvina Novak, ALICE
Paul Hyde, UNEW	Edwin van Hassel, U Antwerpen
Nicolas Guijarro , VNF/DTS Bassin de la Seine/SDVE/PI	Thomas H Zunder, UNEW

Dates of CRISTAL WP4 T4.3.3 BMC Workshops

- Digital Twins, WP5, 28th November 2023
- Synchronodal Corridor Management System, 4th December 2023

Agenda for all workshops

- Overview of WP4.3, Purpose of the Workshop: (UNEW) 10 minutes
- Introductory video on BMC: 2 minutes
- Introduction to the relevant technology: (DEVELOPER) 15-25 minutes
- Co-creation of the BMC on MIRO by all participants with ad hoc conversation and discussion as needed.

Presentations

The technical presentations, which were to be composed of one-third technology, one-third use cases and one-third of customer benefits; are available on request to the project team.

The video explanation of CANVAS is on YouTube here: <https://youtu.be/QoAOzMTLP5s>

6.3 Digital Twins Business Model CANVAS

Digital Twins, WP5, 28th November 2023

FRAUNHOFER made a presentation of the technical, use case and user benefits of the Digital Twins technology developed in WP5. For the BMC it is worth noting the use cases and user benefits presented with 5 of the slides presented, see Figure 33, Figure 34, Figure 35, Figure 36 & Figure 37 below.

Figure 33: Use Cases for DIGITAL TWINS, Italian Pilot (1)

Figure 34: Use Cases for DIGITAL TWINS, Italian Pilot (2)

Figure 35: Use Cases for DIGITAL TWINS, French Pilot

Figure 36: Use Cases for DIGITAL TWINS, Polish Pilot

Customer benefits and definition of customers

Figure 37: Customer Benefits for DIGITAL TWINS

Suitably briefed with the technology context and use cases/benefits the attendees co-created a BMC as follows. Feedback at the end was positive, especially from the technology development team who were pleased to have been able to address business issues not focused on in WP2. The BMC is shown in Figure 38 below.

Figure 38: CRISTAL Digital Twins Business Model CANVAS

The key propositions identified are summarised in Table 19 below, with an assessment of whether the value is perceived, and then if it is realisable within this business model. Note that a perceived value may be realised in collaboration with other technologies or business models, here we assess if the technology in this BMC will do that realisation. Much of the value generated by the DIGITAL TWINS is realisable from the technology in this business model, however, half of that value is perceived and that would need integration with an infrastructure management system or the CRISTAL SCMS or similar for realisation.

Table 19: DIGITAL TWINS Key Propositions and Benefits

Benefits	Perceived Value	Realisable Value
Insights on the current state of the waterways	Y	Y
Transparency - act instead of reacting	Y	Y
Prediction of the water levels for navigability	Y	Y
Insights on the conditions of the infrastructure	Y	Y
Cost reductions and higher reliability, due to higher predictability of transport activities, avoiding/reducing disruptions	Y	
Cost reductions due to predictive maintenance	Y	
By providing services that can incentivize new customers.	Y	
Provide services that lower uncertainties for their business.	Y	
High probabilities of the forecasted data	Y	Y

The BMC assessed the customer segments as follows below in Table 20. We noted that the core customers are direct actors able to directly purchase the offer, with stakeholders who will benefit indirectly, some of whom are very indirect.

Table 20: DIGITAL TWINS Customer Segments

Customer	Actor / Stakeholder	Direct / Indirect
Infrastructure Managers	A	D
Transport operators	S	I
SCMS	A	D
Authorities in charge of general IWT programming/funding	S	I
Mainly “transporteurs fluviaux, transporteurs de passagers, plaisanciers”	S	I
Passenger ships/tourist operators	S	I
Water sports users?	S	I

To deliver the business model, the workshop identified key partners shown below in Table 21. Note that key partners can include both organisations inside and outside of CRISTAL and may even include some that are also customers where they have multiple roles in this domain. Most of the partners are actors, and the interaction is direct.

Table 21: DIGITAL TWINS Key partners

Key partners	Actor / Stakeholder	Direct / Indirect
Software developers	A	D
Entities that could provide useful data that are not being currently considered so much (e.g., from sensor systems, water level monitoring, etc.)	S	I
Sensors owners	A	D
Infrastructure maintenance contractors	A	I
Experts in mathematical models	A	D
Infrastructure manager (to advise on useful functions)	A	D

We can now look at the key activities and resources needed to create the offer. For this BMC they were as shown as essentially functional, see Figure 39.

Figure 39: DIGITAL TWINS Key Activities and Resources

The customer relationships and channels are shown in Figure 40. Note that in one sense they are simple, a monthly contact and then on demand. However, there are also entirely digital relationships, which if some of the ideas about open-source software and social community data repositories were followed, could suggest very different self-organising relationships. Similarly, channels are a mix of wider dissemination but also integration with EuRIS and SCMS where the channel is essentially a third party. The Cost Structure and Revenue boxes remind us that there is a minimum amount of money (resources) needed to develop a working prototype (EU/funding). After that, you can spend more money (resources) to further tailor/improve the product IF there is sufficient demand for the product.

The CANVAS details a fundamental two-part income stream: a one-time payment for the installation of the tech followed by a "monthly" subscription for providing the service. This is all detailed in Figure 41 & Figure 42. Note that there are some ideas for revenue, but there is no cost structure. The discussion at the workshop reported that the CRISTAL digital twins are not seen as a commercial undertaking. There has been talk of releasing code as open source, and indeed it is likely that exploitation of the digital twins will lie in the SCMS or integration using code or algorithms into infrastructure manager systems.

Figure 40: Digital Twins Customer Relationships and Channels

Figure 41: DIGITAL TWINS Cost Structure

Figure 42: DIGITAL TWINS Revenue Streams

6.4 SCMS Business Model CANVAS

Synchromodal Corridor Management System, 4th December 2023

CERTH made a presentation of the technical, use case and user benefits of the SCMS technology developed in WP3. For the BMC it is worth noting the functionalities, potential users and benefits of the SCMS, see Figure 43, Figure 44, Figure 45, and Figure 46 below.

Figure 43: Functionality for SCMS (1)

Figure 44: Functionality for SCMS (2)

Figure 45: Potential Users for SCMS

Figure 46: Potential Benefits for SCMS Users

Suitably briefed with the technology context and use cases/benefits the attendees co-created a BMC as follows. Feedback at the end was positive, especially from the technology development team who were pleased to have been able to address business issues not focused on in WP2. The BMC is shown in Figure 47 below.

The CRISTAL SCMS Business Model Canvas

Figure 47: CRISTAL SCMS Business Model CANVAS

A summary of the key propositions identified is listed in Table 22 below, with an assessment of whether the value is perceived, and then if it is realisable within this business model. Note that a perceived value may be realised in collaboration with other technologies or business models, here we assess if the technology in this BMC will do that realisation. Much of the value generated by the SCMS is realisable from the technology in this business model, fed by EuRIS, other RIS or the CRISTAL digital twins.

Table 22: SCMS Key Propositions and Benefits

Benefits	Perceived Value	Realisable Value
Provide insights about the state of the transport network	Y	Y
Value added over and above EURIS/TAF-TSI etc	Y	Y
Nice to have: Booking resources	Y	
Single point of contact for information about actual and forecast navigability	Y	Y
Dynamic re-routing in response to short-term changes	Y	Y
Synchromodal Forward Routing of Goods	Y	Y
Reduced carbon footprint	Y	Y
Modal shift	Y	Y
Reduced energy bills	Y	Y
Forecast capacity for terminals etc	Y	Y
High probabilities of the forecasted data	Y	Y
Forward operational resource requirement	Y	Y

The BMC assessed the customer segments as follows in Table 23. We noted that the core customers identified are **all** direct actors able to directly purchase and use the offer.

Table 23: SCMS Customer Segments

Customer	Actor / Stakeholder	Direct / Indirect
Freight transport planners	A	D
Freight integrators/brokers	A	D
IWW transport operators	A	D
Transport operators	A	D
Logistics Service Providers	A	D
Regional authorities (top-level policy planning)	A	D

In order to deliver the business model, the workshop identified key partners shown in Table 24. Note that key partners can include both organisations inside and outside of CRISTAL and may even include some that are also customers where they have multiple roles in this domain. The majority of the partners are actors, and the interaction is direct.

Table 24: SCMS Key partners

Key partners	Actor / Stakeholder	Direct / Indirect
Data providers	A	D
IWWT infrastructure manager (including ports) and other transport mode infrastructure manager (for the input)	A	D
Intermodal terminals	A	D
Rail TAF/TSI systems	A	D
software developers	A	D
Digital Twins	A	D
Road ITS systems	A	D
EuRIS	A	D
Entities that could provide useful data that are not being currently considered as such	S	I

We can now look at the key activities and resources needed to create the offer. For this BMC they were as shown in Figure 48 digital, save for partnerships with data source providers, and that may be less traditional if an open community approach was to be adopted.

Figure 48: SCMS Key Activities and Resources

The customer relationships and channels are shown in Figure 49. Note that they are underdeveloped and will need further elaboration in the Living Labs and also in WP3 itself.

The Cost Structure and Revenue boxes remind us that there is a minimum amount of money (resources) needed to develop a working prototype (EU/funding). After that, you can spend more money (resources) to further tailor/improve the product IF there is sufficient demand for the product.

The CANVAS details a fundamental two-part income stream: a one-time payment for the installation of the tech followed by a "monthly" subscription for providing the service.

This is all detailed in Figure 50 & Figure 51. The financial aspects of the BMC are weak and will need addressing further.

Figure 49: SCMS Customer Relationships and Channels

Figure 50: SCMS Cost Structure

Figure 51: SCMS Revenue Streams

7. Quantification method for potential benefits and cost for the CRISTAL solutions

In this chapter, the quantification of the costs and benefits of the new technologies developed for the CRISTAL project is reported. First, the technologies developed in Work Package 2 (WP2) are discussed, followed by a more in-depth analysis of the Digital Twins and the SCMS. Within the CRISTAL project, SCMS and the digital twins are two important technologies that need to be studied. It could be said that the WP2 technologies, in general, provide inputs to the digital twins, which, in turn, can further feed information into the SCMS, whilst some data is also provided to the SCMS directly. A counterargument would be that the WP2 technologies are concrete and realisable, and the digital twins and SCMS are potential users of the data, amongst others. By quantifying the costs and benefits of these technologies, it becomes possible to perform a comprehensive cost-benefit analysis (CBA) to assess whether the technology can be picked up by the market.

This work is based on surveys from October to November sent to the WP2/3/5 technology providers, see the questionnaires in Appendix 0 below.

The CRISTAL technologies are still in the process of being designed and tested, it is difficult to determine their exact costs and benefits; therefore, it can be useful to have a look at existing literature for similar technologies. This will be done for the SCMS and DTs. Additionally, questionnaires were sent to the developers of these CRISTAL technologies to obtain specific data where possible. In a later stage of the project (in Task 10.2), this analysis may be examined with more quantitative data.

WP2 Technologies

In WP2, four different technologies were designed to serve as data inputs (amongst other external sources) for the Digital Twins and SCMS. The DTs convert the data collected via the WP2 technologies into actionable information for infrastructure managers or other beneficiaries. Furthermore, these DTs are integrated with the SCMS, where the outputs generated by the DTs serve as inputs. This establishes a direct link between the WP2 technologies and the SCMS too.

Given the use of these technologies in DTs and SCMS, the costs and benefits in this chapter are discussed at a basic level. There will be a more detailed analysis of the DTs and SCMS, as they play a more important role in processing and utilizing the acquired data. However, it is still essential to discuss each technology separately because they all have their individual advantages for users, as they are designed for different objectives.

7.1 Smart Buoys System

The Smart Buoys System is designed to survey the navigability of controlled waterways. These specialized buoys can monitor water levels, localize buoys, count passing ships, and measure certain environmental parameters, such as water depth, current speed, water and air temperature, and wind direction. In addition, wireless communication with buoys, ships, and sensors is enabled. The primary end-users of this technology are infrastructure managers.

Through the integration of sensors and wireless communication, a Smart Buoys System can enhance the operational efficiency and safety in controlled waterways. These intelligent buoys will be tested at

a designated pilot site situated along the Vistula River in Poland. Here, six buoys will be strategically positioned for 200 kilometres.

Precise details regarding the production costs of the finalized product intended for the market are unknown. However, the prototype of the Smart Buoys is estimated to cost 7.000 to 8.000 euros. This cost includes the sensor component (valued at 5.000 euros), the buoy structure, batteries, and solar panels. If we assume that the prototypes are successful, the cost of manufacturing a smart buoy for an end user or customer could be like the prototype cost. Consequently, the break-even price of a smart buoy reflects the price of the prototype at this stage of the project. A surplus will be added to cover profits. Prospective customers are required not only to purchase buoys but also to subscribe to a Digital Twin or to SCMS, to be able to facilitate the transformation of raw data into available information.

At the test site, there will be a buoy placed every 33,33 kilometres over a length of 200 kilometres. While this arrangement provides a basis for estimating the potential buoy requirement for a customer, it is important to note that there is variation in the need for buoys across different regions. Factors such as drought susceptibility cause different information requirements for various locations. This, in turn, means that different locations require different amounts of buoys.

In Table 25 the costs and benefits of the Smart Buoys System are summarized for the developers.

Table 25: Identified costs and benefits of Smart Buoys System for Developer

Costs	Quantification	Benefits	Quantification
Production of a buoy	7000 – 8000 €	Fee for the purchase of a buoy	7000 – 8000 € + additional costs + surplus for profits
		After-Sales Service fees	Depends on necessary maintenance, upgrades, and repairs

In Table 26 this is done from the point of view of the users of the technology. The quantification of the benefits for users is not possible at this moment; therefore, quantification will be replaced by a qualitative explanation.

Table 26: Identified costs and benefits of Smart Buoys System for users.

Costs	Quantification	Benefits	Motivation
Purchase of a smart buoy	7000 – 8000 € + surplus	Real-time information on water levels, buoy localization, passing ships, and certain environmental parameters	This information is valuable as it will better inform barge operators and the infrastructure managers about the listed parameters. This information could be used to better plan and optimize cargo loading, faster decision-making for routes, and avoid groundings and waiting times.

Subscription to Digital Twin	To be determined in a later stage	Traffic monitoring, navigability alerts and visualization of the river	This data is useful to reduce congestion at key points and avoid collisions or other accidents. It will also make more efficient route planning possible.
After-sales service costs	Depends on necessary maintenance, repairs, and updates	Monitoring environmental parameters	Monitoring environmental parameters such as water depth, current speed, water and air temperature, and wind direction can improve safety, efficiency, maintenance planning, and decision making.
Implementation cost	Depends on factors such as location	Wireless communication	Efficient communication between vessels helps coordination and thus creates time savings. It also offers possibilities for emergency responses.

7.2 Fibre Optic Sensors

Fibre Optic Sensors (FOS) is a technology developed to monitor the navigability of free-flowing waterways. These sensors utilize strategically placed weight sensors at critical section lines, to detect sand pileups in real-time. This timely detection enables more efficient dredging planning and better reliability of navigability forecasting, thereby minimizing the productivity losses and accidents caused by these obstructions. The primary end users of the FOS are waterway managers and calamity abatement operators. Barge operators and logistics service providers are other beneficiaries of this technology. Testing of this technology is planned for pilot sites located in Italy .

The FOS operation involves interconnected pads that are linked through a cable line. The required number of pads varies based on the length and dimensions of the critical section line. Like other technologies within WP2, the FOS collects data but does not autonomously transmit it. The responsibility of reporting this data to end users rests on a Digital Twin system. Consequently, customers (i.e. inland waterway managers) will acquire the FOS and can subscribe to a Digital Twin to use the collected data for informed decision-making¹.

The cost for the submerged materials for the FOS at the pilot site in Italy is estimated to be around 250.000 euros for the critical section necessitating five weighing stations. Additionally, the cost for the Data Acquisition System is assumed to be 50.000 euros. Only one system is necessary regardless of the number of monitored critical sections. End users of the FOS will have to cover these costs and pay a surplus for profits. Additional costs are caused by the installation of the FOS, which will be 200.000 euros minimum upfront.

¹ if I am an IM and I buy FOS technology, rough data are available for me and are sent (directly or through my organization) to DT. Eventually I can subscribe to DT to get processed data.

It's crucial to highlight that the mentioned costs can vary depending on the width of the river at the monitoring location, as the entire width of the river needs to be covered. Also, not all the associated costs are included in this estimate, and the overall expenses could be significantly higher depending, for example, on the type of infrastructure chosen to house the FOS system. Since the system is still in the prototype phase, the exact costs are not clear yet.

Table 27 provides a summary of the costs and benefits associated with the FOS from the perspective of the developers.

Table 27: Identified costs and benefits of Fibre Optic Sensor for Developers

Costs	Quantification	Benefits	Quantification
Production of a fibre optic sensor	250.000 € + 50.000 € + other costs	Purchase of a fibre optic sensor	300.000 € + other costs + surplus for profit
		After-sales service fee	Depends on necessary maintenance, upgrades, and repairs

Table 28 summarizes the perspective of the technology users. Again, it is important to note that quantification is not always possible at this stage of the project. Therefore, some quantifications will be replaced by a qualitative explanation.

Table 28: Identified costs and benefits of Fibre Optic Sensors (waterway managers and barge operators)

Costs	Quantification	Benefits	Quantification
Purchase of Fibre Optic Sensors	300.000 € + other costs + surplus for profit	Predictive dredging	Optimizing dredging schedules prevents emergency and unnecessary dredging costs, enhances safety by maintaining navigable waterways, and boosts productivity by planning dredging operations to minimize disruptions to planned traffic, leading to significant time savings.
Subscription to Digital Twin	To be determined	Better maintained waterway depth	A more stable waterway depth allows a more optimal payload for inland vessels operated on the inland waterway network.
After-sales service costs	Depends on necessary maintenance,		

	upgrades, and repairs		
Implementation cost	200.000 €		

7.3 Subsurface Inspection Radar

Subsurface Inspection Radars (SIR) enable the inspection of engineered structures, such as locks, dams, and quay walls. These radars can detect potential subsurface defects or issues that require preventive actions. Furthermore, via data processing, it is possible to map existing structures properly. This is helpful for the future maintenance of older locks. The end users of this technology are the infrastructure managers responsible for overseeing these structures. This technology will be implemented at the pilot site in France.

Users of the SIR will not purchase the SIR but rather purchase a survey done with SIR by a provider. The data collected via this inspection will be transmitted to DTs, where it can be transformed into usable information. The cost of operating the system to survey one lock is 9.900 euros, the survey takes 5 days. With a surplus of 5.100 euros, the inland waterway manager will pay 15.000 euros per survey for a lock, dam, or quay wall. Within this surplus, 2.500 euros are allocated specifically to data visualization and report provisions. The remaining surplus is used to cover various expenses, including company overheads, advertising efforts, and profit margins. Typically, surveys are required every 8 to 10 years for most locks. However, certain locks will undergo annual inspections depending on the available resources. The target is to survey 20 locks per year, which would generate an income of 300.000 euros per year for the providers of the technology.

Table 29 discusses the costs and benefits of the Subsurface Inspection Radar for the developers.

Table 29: Identified costs and benefits of Subsurface Inspection Radar for Developers

Costs	Quantification	Benefits	Quantification
Cost to survey a lock	9.900 €	Purchase of a survey with SIR	15.000 €
Other costs	5.100 € - profit		

Table 30 does this for the users. The benefits for the users will be explained from a qualitative point of view as quantification is not yet possible.

Table 30: Identified costs and benefits of Subsurface Inspection Radar for Users

Costs	Quantification	Benefits	Quantification
Purchase of a survey with SIR	15.000 €	Possibility to detect defects	Cost and time savings from reduced repairs and minimized disruptions, along with prolonged asset

Costs	Quantification	Benefits	Quantification
			lifespan due to timely maintenance.
Subscription to Digital Twin	To be determined	Possibility to map out existing locks	Helps to improve infrastructure planning and resource allocation. It also improves safety measures for the older locks. The mapping of locks also helps improve the accuracy of the DTs and SCMS.
After-sales service cost	Depends on required maintenance, upgrades, and repairs		
Implementation cost	To be determined		

7.4 Acoustic Emission System

Acoustic Emission System (AES) facilitates monitoring as well as preventive and predictive maintenance of water lock gates. This system is mainly useful to relevant maintenance managers, and calamity abatement operators for efficient maintenance planning and risk mitigation. The designated pilot site for this technology are in France and Italy.

The production cost of an Acoustic Emission System is 15.338,75 euros, this also includes travel costs of 1.587 euros for the implementation of the system. Accurate use of AES systems necessitates the installation of four sensors per door. Consequently, a lock featuring four doors must be equipped with a total of sixteen sensors to ensure complete monitoring coverage. Similar to the previous technologies, the AES will only collect data. This data will then be transformed into actionable information in the DTs.

Table 31 summarizes the costs and benefits of the AES for the developer, the non-quantifiable parameters will be given a qualitative explanation.

Table 31: Identified costs and benefits of Acoustic Emission System for Developers

Costs	Quantification	Benefits	Quantification
Production of AES	15.338,75 €	Purchase of AES	15.338,75 € + other costs + surplus for profit
		After-sale service fees	Depends on necessary maintenance, upgrades, and repairs

Table 32 summarizes the costs and benefits of the AES for the users.

Table 32: Identified costs and benefits of Acoustic Emission System for Users

Costs	Quantification	Benefits	Quantification
Purchase of AES	15.338,75 € + other costs + surplus for profit	Monitoring lock gates	Reduces downtime and related costs due to predictive maintenance. Optimizes workflow and decision-making. It also enhances safety.
Subscription to Digital Twin	To be determined		
After-sale service cost	Depends on required maintenance, upgrades, and repairs		
Implementation cost	To be determined		

7.5 Digital Twins (DTs)

A digital twin is the digital representation of real-world equipment, devices, or systems (Augustine, 2020). This technology improves performance, generates savings, and increases operational flexibility through real-time updates that are accessible to all users (Ibrion et al., 2019). Via WP2 technologies, the main use of DTs will be preventive maintenance and navigability forecasting, with infrastructure managers and transport operators as the most important users. The Digital Twins will be used at all pilot sites, with different use cases.

Cost Analysis

For the developers of the DTs, the primary cost will be the production cost of the digital solution, which may comprise hardware and software costs. When offering them to end users, the selling price will

have to cover these production costs and an additional margin for profit. The exact production cost of a digital twin is unknown at this point of the project, however the cost of producing a prototype is. This is estimated to be 414.457 euros. It is not possible to derive the cost of the final product from this as the final product will incur higher costs due to factors such as customization, scalability, integration etc. However, if the prototype is successful, it is possible to assume that the cost of the production of a product will be the cost of this prototype adjusted with a multiplier based on these factors.

As mentioned above, the DTs use data from the WP2 technologies to create an output. There are costs related to using these different technologies as inputs. These costs will be for the use of the technology (e.g., subscription fee), data transmission, usage of the data, and customization, if necessary. In the questionnaire for the Digital Twins, Fraunhofer indicated that only personnel costs are relevant in this context. Both end users and developers can bear these costs. If developers cover these expenses, the purchase price will naturally reflect this decision. Consequently, these costs have been included in the table outlining costs and benefits for users because they will eventually cover these costs even if it is originally the responsibility of the developers.

Other important costs for customers when purchasing this new technology are the ongoing costs, such as maintenance fees, and implementation costs. However, it is not possible to derive these now as the DTs are currently still in the prototype development phase.

Benefit Analysis

The most important benefit for the users of a digital twin is its ability to simulate the behaviours of the infrastructure. This simulation allows for the anticipation of future issues and opportunities, as supported by various studies (Ambra et al., 2019; Attaran & Celik, 2023; Kaewunruen et al., 2021). In the CRISTAL project, the Digital Twins will enable real-time monitoring and analysis, predictive maintenance, traffic management, resource allocation, and data-driven decision-making. These functionalities translate into reduced waiting times at locks due to maintenance, the potential for early cargo shifting to different transportation modes, and the availability of data for long-term analysis and predictions. Consequently, it will also lead to cost savings for the users.

From the developers' perspective, the primary benefit lies in the revenue generated from the Digital Twins. While the specific revenue model has not been established, there are several potential approaches. Subscription-based models, value-based pricing, and outcome-based pricing are the main options (part 2022). Additionally, income can be generated by offering services such as data analytics and insights or other value-added services. Lastly, a way for the developers to generate revenue is by charging a fee to access and utilize the insights and information generated by the Digital Twins and offering it as a service to users or the SCMS.

Results and discussion

Based on the analyses above, it is possible to conclude that the Digital Twins can offer substantial benefits to both the developers and end-users.

For end-users, the ability to simulate infrastructure behaviours provides important benefits, including the prediction of future problems and opportunities. Real-time monitoring, predictive maintenance, efficient traffic management, and data-driven decision-making contribute to reduced waiting times, early cargo shifting options and comprehensive data. These advantages not only enhance operational

efficiency but also lead to significant cost savings over time, making the investment in Digital Twins possibly worthwhile.

From the developers' perspective, revenue generation is the primary benefit. While the exact revenue model is yet to be determined, potential approaches include subscription-based models, value-based pricing, and outcome-based pricing. Moreover, developers can offer additional services like data analytics and insights, further enhancing their income streams.

Considering the benefits outlined for both end-users and developers, it is important to note that the exact costs associated with implementing Digital Twins remain unknown within the project. While the benefits are substantial, it is necessary to acknowledge the possibility that the costs could outweigh these benefits if they are excessively high. Financial planning, cost control, and ongoing cost-benefit analyses are tools to ensure that the implementation remains economically viable and advantageous for all stakeholders involved.

Table 33 gives an overview of the above-mentioned costs and benefits for the developer of the DTs.

Table 33: Identified costs and benefits of Digital Twins for Developers

Costs	Quantification/description	Benefits	Quantification/description
Production of a DTs	414.457 * multiplier	Purchase of/subscription to DTs	A function of the production cost + surplus for other costs and profit (depends on revenue model)
		Use of data for SCMS	To be determined

Table 34 does the same from the point of view of the users or customers. Due to a shortage of exact numbers, the table includes a description of the elements.

Table 34: Identified costs and benefits of Digital Twin for Users

Costs	Quantification/description	Benefits	Quantification/description
Purchase of/subscription to DTs	A function of the production cost + surplus for other costs and profit (depends on revenue model)	Real-Time monitoring and analysis	This provides immediate insights into the current state of operations, enabling quick response to changing conditions.
Implementation costs	Not determined in the research phase	Predictive maintenance	It minimizes operational disruptions, enhances safety, and lowers maintenance costs by addressing issues before they escalate.

Costs	Quantification/description	Benefits	Quantification/description
After-sales costs (e.g., maintenance fees)	Not determined in the research phase	Traffic management	It enables preventing collisions, managing navigation routes, and ensuring smooth flow of goods. It optimizes the use of available infrastructure and resources.
Cost to use other technologies as input (CRISTAL technologies and external sources)	Only personnel costs	Resource allocation	This leads to cost savings, improved productivity, and better utilization of assets.
		Data-driven decision making	It enables evidence decision-making making, strategic planning, and performance optimization.

7.6 Synchronodal Corridor Management System (SCMS)

The SCMS strives to enhance transportation operations through real-time information, dynamic planning, and optimal resource utilization. Its primary objective is to make transportation more efficient and cost-effective by using synchronodal transport. Unlike traditional intermodal transport, synchronodality enables the dynamic redirection of cargo to more favourable routes or modes as needed, providing a flexible and responsive solution. Within the CRISTAL project, the SCMS is designed from the perspective of inland navigation, where new CRISTAL technologies are used as data inputs. The pilot countries are Italy, Poland, and France (CERTH, 2023).

Although the concept of synchronodality is still relatively new, research has already been conducted on its (possible) costs and benefits. The focus of most papers is on benefits. To gain insight into the costs and benefits of the SCMS, it is interesting to view the existing literature on synchronodality in general. The SCMS will make synchronodality possible for inland navigation in new locations; therefore, the impact of SCMS is directly related to the impact of synchronodality.

Agbo and Zhang (2017) emphasize the importance of considering geographical features when implementing synchronodality in a corridor. Essential components for successful synchronodality include a sea or maritime port, navigable inland waterways, a well-developed railway system, and road transport infrastructure. The three pilot sites—France, Poland, and Italy—exhibit distinct transport networks, influencing the feasibility of synchronodality and thus the effect of the SCMS.

France stands out as a promising location for synchronodality with its seaports, extensive inland waterways, robust rail infrastructure, and road transport. While road transport currently prevails, the presence of well-established networks for other modes lays a strong foundation for synchronodality.

Poland's strategic location, connecting with seaports through its corridor, presents opportunities for both road and rail transport. However, investments are required to elevate inland waterways, only 6% of which are internationally significant, to a strategic level for synchromodality.

Italy has a robust railway and road network, with a small inland waterway network connecting to a seaport. Although limited in size, these inland waterways hold the potential for synchromodality at specific locations within Italy.

In essence, the SCMS aims to enable synchromodality in new inland navigation locations.

Cost Analysis

The development and implementation of the SCMS involves various costs from different aspects.

For synchromodality to become possible and efficient, the system used for transport planning must have the correct inputs to receive the necessary data as quickly as possible (where possible in real-time) and with the required quality. This information is necessary about infrastructure, transport modes, services and prices, transit, weather conditions, and so on (Agbo & Zhang, 2017). In the CRISTAL project, the Digital Twins will be used as data input, alongside external data sources for other information and modes of transport. Furthermore, some sensor data from technologies are directly sent to SCMS. Integration costs for the technologies, such as Fibre Optic Sensors, Smart Buoy System, and Acoustic Emission Technology, are primarily personnel-related, with no additional direct costs foreseen. The integration with external sources, like Transport Management Systems and GIS, may involve fees depending on decisions made during platform development.

Additionally, investments in infrastructure, especially in regions lacking vital components such as navigable waterways, might create significant costs for implementing synchromodal systems, as observed in Poland, where investments in inland waterways are necessary.

CERTH's completed questionnaire outlines key cost categories. Primarily, staffing costs are highlighted, including personnel for system development, validation, testing, and maintenance/operation. The next category is the expenses associated with connecting to external platforms for data acquisition, as previously mentioned. Additionally, costs for promotion and scientific dissemination are identified. Lastly, the questionnaire mentions costs related to external hosting services or in-house hosting equipment/software. Currently, during the project phase, in-house hosting incurs no additional costs apart from personnel. Only upon entering the commercial exploitation phase can the precise other costs be determined. However, the breakdown of annual expenses indicates that major future costs will revolve around personnel and cloud hosting services.

Ongoing maintenance or subscription fees are anticipated during the commercial exploitation phase, though specific details and amounts are yet to be determined. Ongoing costs post-SCMS production, including staff, promotion, hosting, and further development, are also expected.

In summary, the SCMS development and implementation involves various costs, with personnel costs and potential cloud hosting services standing out as significant contributors to future expenditures. The commercial exploitation phase is expected to introduce maintenance fees, but specific details on various ongoing costs remain to be determined.

In Table 35 the costs of SCMS for the developers are summarized. No quantification is possible based on current knowledge. However, in the following part estimation will be made.

Table 35: Identified costs of SCMS for developers.

Costs	Quantification
Development and Implementation	Unknown at this stage of the project
Staffing Costs for development	Staff count and associated salaries
Staffing costs for maintenance and operation	Staff count and associated salaries
Data Acquisition (CRISTAL technologies)	Personnel cost
Data Acquisition (external sources)	Connection expenses to external platforms
Promotion and Scientific Dissemination	Unknown at this stage of the project
Hosting Services	Hosting fees and equipment/software costs
Future Ongoing Costs	Unknown at this stage of the project

In Table 36 the same summary is made but from the perspective of the users.

Table 36: Identified costs of SCMS for users.

Costs	Quantification
Purchase/subscription depends on the chosen revenue model)	Unknown at this stage of the project
Investment in infrastructure	Investments necessary to be able to properly implement SCMS
Implementation cost	Unknown at this stage of the project and depends on location
Maintenance fee	Unknown at this stage of the project

Benefit Analysis

The benefits of synchromodality, and consequently, SCMS, can be classified into economic, social, and environmental dimensions. Economically, synchromodality optimizes service line occupancies and reduces delivery times, contributing to economic efficiency. From a social perspective, it optimizes network flows, reduces road traffic, alleviates congestion, and minimizes accidents. Another benefit to mention is that infrastructure managers view SCMS as a way to cope with disruptions more efficiently. Furthermore, there are environmental benefits, including a reduction in pollutants and CO₂ air emissions, noise pollution from trucks, and a modal shift away from road transport, ultimately leading to a more sustainable transportation system (Agbo & Zhang, 2017; Zhang & Pel, 2016).

Incorporating Digital Twins technology into the SCMS enhances its efficiency by providing real-time and forecasted data on infrastructure health, weather conditions, navigability, and other essential factors. This integration ensures the accuracy and responsiveness of the system, leading to enhanced decision-making capabilities and further amplifying the benefits of synchromodality.

The questionnaire filled out by CERTH provides further insights. The system helps identify and mitigate risks in the supply chain, offering benefits such as decreased delays, reliable time estimations, enhanced visibility of alternatives during disruptions, and reduced environmental impact. Specific examples of time and resource savings include efficient route planning in response to disruptions, minimizing delays, and proposing alternative modes of transport. Additionally, implementation enhances customer satisfaction in the supply chain by minimizing uncertainty regarding river navigability and operational disruptions, making businesses more reliable and flexible.

The revenue model of the SCMS has not yet been defined in the project. Possibilities include but are not limited to, a subscription-based model, a pay-per-use model, a licensing model, or API usage fees. Ongoing support and updates are planned, although specific details are yet to be defined.

In summary, the Synchromodal Corridor Management System can contribute to improving the economic, social, and environmental facets of transportation. While specific revenue details have not yet been decided, SCMS demonstrates benefits for users in risk mitigation, improved reliability, reduced waiting times, and long-term sustainability. Within the context of the CRISTAL project, the most important benefits will be the reduction in waiting time, the positive effect on the modal shift, and the improvement of the reliability of transport, as these most align with the goals of the project.

Table 37 summarizes the benefits of SCMS for the developers.

Table 37: Identified benefits of SCMS for developers.

Benefits	Quantification
Revenue directly from SCMS	Depends on the revenue model (subscription-based, pay-per-use, etc.). This is unknown at this stage of the project
After-sales services (ongoing support and updates)	Unknown at this stage of the project
API usage fees	Possible fee for using the SCMS APIs (by other platforms) in order to receive the output of the synchromodal route planning service (proposed alternatives) or to receive notifications from the inventory of alerts or the analytics from the SCMS observatory. This is unknown at this stage of the project

Table 38 summarizes the benefits of the SCMS for users. Quantification is not possible at this moment, so a qualitative explanation is given for each benefit. In the next part, the most relevant benefits will be quantified using estimates.

Table 38: Identified benefits of SCMS for the users.

Benefits	Clarification
Social benefits	Due to the reduction in road traffic, congestion, and accidents
Improved sustainability and modal split	Due to the reduction in emissions, noise pollution from trucks, and improved modal shift away from the road
Decrease in costs	Due to improved efficiency and a decrease in external costs
Decrease in waiting times/delays	Due to improved efficiency
Improved reliability	Due to improved efficiency and thus reduction of disruptions

Quantification

As mentioned before, both the WP2 technologies and the DTs are inputs for the SCMS. This means that the main benefits of these technologies are included in the functionality of the SCMS. Therefore, it is possible to quantify the impact of all the CRISTAL innovations by developing a Social Cost Benefit Analysis (SCBA) for the SCMS. This means that all the costs of developing the SCMS, DTs, and WP2 technologies are considered along with the benefits of all the technologies at the supply chain level. These benefits are a reduction in waiting time, an improvement of reliability and capacity of IWT, even during disruptions, and the promotion of a modal shift towards IWT, as a more sustainable and environmentally friendly mode of transport.

To make a first preliminary assessment of the potential benefits of the CRISTAL innovations a set of assumptions need to be made (both in terms of cost and effectiveness). This is done because no information is available to date (January 2024) about the possible impacts. In a later stage in the project (WP10) these numbers can be adjusted and corrected, and the calculations can be updated.

Table 39: Input parameters for the SCBA of the SMCS.

Costs	Quantification	Benefits	Quantification
Fixed costs to build all the technology	600.000 €	Reduction in waiting time	A reduction in waiting time of 20% can be achieved by using SCMS.
Operational costs of all implemented technology	15.000 €/year	Percentage of non-reliable transport	10%

Costs	Quantification	Benefits	Quantification
Cost of integrating and maintaining the WP2 technologies in SCMS	5.000 €/year	Increased corridor capacity even during extreme weather events	
Cost of including DTs in SCMS	5.000 €/year	Reduction of CO ₂ emissions per ton*km	
		Infrastructure maintenance optimization	

With the data of Table 39 the first version of a SCBA of the SCMS is developed. The main outcome can be seen in Figure 53.

For this SCBA a hypothetical transport corridor is assumed in which road transport is 100 km, while the IWT option is 100 km with 25 km of post haulage (see Figure 52).

Figure 52: Transport corridor in which the SMCS is applied.

For both transport chains, the generalized costs are computed based on the same formulations as those used by Doll et al (Doll et al., 2022.). The full description of the modelling work can be found in Appendices

Annex I: Modelling **Formulas.**

Based on the calculated generalized cost the mode choice can be computed based on:

$$P_{(road)} = e^{(-\mu \cdot GC_{(road)})} / (e^{(-\mu \cdot GC_{(road)})} + e^{(-\mu \cdot GC_{(IWT)})}) \tag{1}$$

$$P_{(iwt)} = e^{(-\mu \cdot GC_{(iwt)})} / (e^{(-\mu \cdot GC_{(road)})} + e^{(-\mu \cdot GC_{(IWT)})}) \tag{2}$$

The main benefits of the full SCMS are a reduction in waiting time during IWT transport and an improvement in reliability. In the current status of the project, the current reliability of the transport system is unknown and therefore an assumption is made that the current transport system is unreliable

and that the free flow lead time will be increased by 20% for road transport and 30% for IWT. By using the SCMS the overall lead time in IWT is reduced by 20% and the total variance in transport time is reduced from 30% to 10%.²

Next to the quantification of the private benefits, the social benefits are also included in the analysis. These social benefits are computed as the saved external cost due to the implementation of the SCMS. These savings on external costs (congestion, climate change (CO₂), emissions, infrastructure damage, noise, accidents) are determined based on the data from (van Hassel et al., 2015) and these costs are also included in the generalized cost calculations.

In order to compute the net benefits of the full SCMS an assumption is made about the transport volume on the corridor. This assumption is that there is 20.000 TEUs are shipped per year, along with 10.000 tonnes of dry bulk. Next to that, a yearly increase of 2% in transport demand is taken (doll et al 2022) and all costs and benefits are depreciated by 4% per year.³

Based on all the above inputs, the NPV calculations can be made. The main result of this can be seen in Figure 53. The detailed formulae can be found in appendix I, where the main calculations are shown.

Figure 53: SCBA result of the SCMS (left with base cargo volumes, right half of the assumed cargo volumes).

From Figure 53 it can be observed that the project could have net benefits of 135.225 €. For this project, the IRR is 4,51% and the payback period is 12,5 years. It must be noted that the net benefits are highly dependent on the actual transport volume on the corridor. If the transport volume is halved (10.000 TEUs and 5.000 tonnes) the net benefits drop to -222.595 €. So, the use of the full SCMS will only be beneficial in terms of return on investment if the corridor usage is high enough.

² These values can be changed and updated in a later stage in the project.

³ Also these cost can be changed if new and better insights are available.

There are also assumptions made in relation to the effectiveness of the CRISTAL innovations. In Table 40 below the effect of reducing the effectiveness can be observed.

Table 40: SCMS Overall Impact

Benefits of SCMS	Reduction in waiting time	20%	10%	5%	2,5%
	percentage of transport that is not reliable	10%	5%	2,5%	1,25%
SCBA result of the full SCMS		€ 133.518	€ 81.924	€ 59.194	€ 48.589

From the table can be concluded that the overall impact is much less than that cargo volumes. Even if the effectiveness is not very great, there are still some overall benefits to be obtained.

A last main assumption that was made was about the reliability of the IWT in the pilot area. In the table below it can be observed how the SCBA of the SCMS is impacted if the initial IWT reliability is higher than what is assumed. In these calculations the other parameters are set at the initial assumed values.

Table 41: SCMS, SCBA, IWT reliability

Variance in waiting time road	20%	20%	20%
Variance in waiting time IWT	30%	20%	10%
SCBA result of the full SCMS	€ 133.518	-€ 80.147	-€ 288.668

From the Table 41 above it can be concluded that the effectiveness of the full SMCS is reduced if the initial reliability of inland waterway transport is higher than assumed. This means that the impact of the full SCMS is effective if the current IWT system is not performing well. That means that any improvement (even small) can contribute to a positive SCBA. If the current IWT system is reliable then the SCMS needs to be very efficient to obtain a positive SCBA.

These results that are presented here are the first results and are based on the first insights obtained in the project and assumptions made about the effectiveness of the innovations. If better and/or more output becomes available, the analysis can be updated. What is done is a sensitivity analysis to identify how the SCMS behaves with varying inputs. This can be done in deliverable D10.1

Results and discussion

In this chapter, the costs and benefits of the SCMS for the users and the developers were discussed. Additionally, a quantification was made of the parameters that are useful for a SCBA, based on estimations that can be refined in the future.

The SCMS will make synchro-modality possible for inland navigation in new locations; therefore, the impact of SCMS is directly related to the impact of synchro-modality. Within the context of the CRISTAL project, the most important benefits will be the reduction in waiting time, the positive effect on the modal shift, and the improvement of the reliability of transport, as these most align with the goals of the project.

Table 37 and Table 38 summarize the benefits of SCMS. SCMS demonstrates benefits for users in risk mitigation, improved reliability, reduced waiting times, and improved sustainability. Revenue directly from SCMS for the developers depends on the revenue model (subscription-based, pay-per-use, etc.), which is unknown at this stage of the project. After-sales services (ongoing support and updates) and API usage fees are also unknown at this stage of the project.

In contrast, Table 35 and Table 36 summarize the costs of SCMS. For the developers, the costs should be covered by the payments they will receive from the users. This means that the usage of SCMS will incur costs for the users, depending on the revenue model. Implementation costs, necessary costs to improve infrastructure, and maintenance fees are also necessary to consider for the users.

For it to be interesting for potential users to invest in this technology, it is important that the benefits outweigh the costs. The quantification shows that this will only be the case if the transport volume in the corridor is high enough and that the current IWT system can be considered as unreliable (high variance in transport time). Due to the diversity in locations where the SCMS will be used, it is also possible to conclude that the weight of the benefits will differ per location. For potential users, it will be important to evaluate if the SCMS will be useful enough in the selected area to justify the necessary costs.

8. Conclusions

Difficulties encountered.

We decided that the flow of WP4.3 should be amended so that T4.3.1 followed T4.3.2 and T4.3.3. This would enable the workshop-based 'bottom-up' CANVAS work to inform the quantitative modelling of T4.3.1.

Good practices that should be established.

MIRO made a good platform for the delivery of a pan-European workshop that replicated the physical process of a "wall" and "Post-it notes".

It was important to brief the technology development teams on both the need to present the technology and also to think about and present use cases and customer benefits, in other words, to focus on the demand side and the offer.

It was very important to fully brief the team on the actual process of a CANVAS BMC workshop, which was done with presentations leading up to the workshop, briefing documents and finally the very good video on YouTube.

Feedback at the end was positive, especially from the technology development teams who were pleased to have been able to address business issues not focused on in WP2.

Main Conclusions

The business model canvas is a step towards the concept of a *business ecosystem* for incorporating innovations (Moore, 1993) and strengthening their market position. The work in WP4.3 has started to bring synergies of the different actors and stakeholders together towards a common innovation and shared benefit. However, this Phase 4 Design process has just started, and as described in the Objectives and Figure 4 on page 15 above, the design of the BMC needs to now be validated by a Joint Workshop and then continued in WP4.4 in the Living Labs. There are noticeable absences of cost and revenue in most of the BMCs. The delineation between the customer segments is blurred and ambiguous. For the BMC to move to Phase 4 Implementation in WPs 6-9, further syncretic and standardised versions will be needed. This work will be done in WP4.4, however, the underlying technical capability of the innovations needs further examination in WP2, WP3 and WP5.

A BMC process should review the degree to which actors and stakeholders are key, and the nature of those stakeholders, actors or stakeholders as discussed in Section 3.2 above on page 13. We have done this for each BMC and found that not only are the actors and stakeholders different per technology, but that they vary in the degree to which they are direct or indirect customers of the technology or solution. A similar analysis of key partners on the supply side shows similar variance. In most but not all BMC there is a symbiotic relationship with the infrastructure managers in that they appear as key partners enabling the BMC to function but also as customers; in practice this may disappear in a more developed business model where the information and data flows are processed by a DT or the SCMS as a service.

For evaluation and validation can proceed in WP10, T10.2 shall raise a series of open questions for the BMCs. The ability of the technical and pilot WPs to meet those open questions will form the evaluation in 10.2, with a repeated SCBA.

In this deliverable, the overall costs and benefits of the SCMS for the users and the developers are determined. The SCMS is the development in the CRISTAL project that targets the supply chain function of the inland waterway network (shippers, barge operators, etc.) while it also includes the different CRISTAL innovations which the FOS, AES, SB, SIR, and DTs.

All of these innovations have in common that they could contribute to a reduction in waiting time, and the improvement of the reliability of inland waterway transport, which should lead to a positive effect on the modal shift and a reduction in external costs. From the first results, it can be concluded that the SCMS demonstrates net benefits (135.225 € after a period of 20 years). The main benefits are obtained in risk mitigation, improved reliability, reduced waiting times, and improved sustainability. The obtained net benefits are also very sensitive to the transport volume in the corridor.

It also needs to be mentioned that some of the parameters are based on estimations (such as the cargo flow data) and preliminary results of the cost of the different technologies. In a later stage of the project, the data can be refined (also per region) and updated (in WP10).

The work reported in this deliverable met the objectives of Task 4.3 in the CRISTAL project effectively and provided liaison and co-creation of business models and associated SCBA for all technology providers in WPs 2/3/5 and in most cases drew the partners attention to ongoing operational and commercial opportunities. It has provided Task 4.4 of the project an extensive set of BMC, still formative and in development, that can be further elaborated and developed in the LL and in the pilots. It has provided the basis for evaluation in Task 10.2 and will form part of the dissemination and also evaluation of the project in WP10 and WP11.

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10. Appendices

Annex I: Modelling Formulas

A.1 Generalised cost

The cost functions for road, rail and IWT are taken from van Hassel et al. (2016a) and adapted to incorporate cost changes due to possible future developments. These cost functions are described in detail in the next sections.

A.1.1 Road transport

The generalised cost function of road transport can be seen in equation 1.

$$GC_{road,i} = C_{road,i} + 2 \cdot C_{handling,i} + T_{road} \cdot VoT_i \quad (1)$$

In which

$GC_{road,i}$ is the generalised cost road transport for commodity type i [1][1] [EUR/load unit]

$C_{road,i}$ is the out-of-pocket cost for commodity type i [EUR/ Load unit]

$C_{Handling,i}$ is the handling cost per commodity type i [EUR/Load unit]

T_{road} is the total transport time via road transport [h]

VoT_i is the value of time for commodity type i [EUR/(unit.h)].

Formula 2 gives the equation to calculate the out-of-pocket road transport cost (C_{Road}).

$$C_{Road,i} = \frac{D_{road} \cdot DC_{road,i} \cdot (1 + P_{DCR_VAR,i}) + (T_{Road,driving} + T_{congestion} + T_{handle}) \cdot HC_{road,i} \cdot (1 + P_{HCR_VAR,i}) + T_{Road,resting} \cdot \frac{1}{2} \cdot HC_{road,i} \cdot (1 + P_{HCR_VAR,i})}{Cap_{Road,i} \cdot (1 + P_{CR_VAR,i})} \quad (2)$$

In which

D_{Road} is the road distance between origin and destination [km]

$DC_{road,i}$ is the road distance cost [EUR/km] for commodity type i

$P_{DCR_VAR,i}$ is the add-on for the cost per kilometre for road transport dependent on a future scenario for commodity type i [%],

$P_{HCR_VAR,i}$ is the add-on for the cost per hour for road transport dependent on a future scenario for commodity type i [%]

$P_{CR_VAR,i}$ is the add-on for the load capacity for road transport dependent on a future scenario for commodity type i [%]

$T_{road, driving}$ is the total driving time [h]

$T_{congestion}$ is the congestion time on the road [h]

T_{handle} is the handling time [h]

$HC_{road,i}$ is the hour cost component for commodity type i [EUR/h]

$T_{road,resting}$ is the total resting time [h]

$Cap_{Road,i}$ is the load capacity of a truck for commodity type i [TEU or ton] and

The total road time (T_{Road}) can be calculated with formula 3.

$$T_{road} = T_{road,driving} + T_{road,resting} + T_{cong} \cdot (1 + P_{CTR_VAR,i}) + T_{handle} \quad (3)$$

The road driving time can be calculated with formula 4. In which $P_{CTR_VAR,i}$ is the add-on for the congestion time for road transport dependent on a future scenario for commodity type i [%].

$$T_{road,driving} = \frac{D_{road}}{V_{road}} \quad (4)$$

V_{road} is the driving speed of a truck [km/h] and can be calculated with formula 5 (van Dorsser, 2006).

$$V_{road} = C_1 + C_2 \cdot \text{TANH}(D_{road} \cdot C_3) \quad (5)$$

In which C_1 = constant at 37.274 , C_2 = constant at 45.638 and C_3 = constant at 0.01189

The calculation also includes the resting times. This is done because some road distances are over 1,000 kms. This implies that the maximum driving time allowance per day will be breached if no resting is included. In formula 6, the function to determine the resting time (per 24 hours) is given.

$$(T_{road,driving} < 4.5h \rightarrow T_{road,resting} = 0) \wedge (T_{road,driving} < 9h \rightarrow T_{road,resting} = 0.75) \wedge (T_{road,driving} > 9h \rightarrow T_{road,resting} = 13.5) \quad (6)$$

A.1.2 IWT transport

For IWT transport, we again distinguish among three options: Unimodal transport, maritime intermodal transport and continental intermodal transport.

Unimodal transport

The cost structure to calculate generalised cost of IWT transport is given in formula 7.

$$GC_{IWT} = C_{IWT}(CEMT) + C_{Handling_IWT} + T_{UM_IWT} \cdot VoT \quad (7)$$

This cost structure is the same as for rail transport. However, the cost structure of the IWT out-of-pocket cost depends on the maximum allowable dimensions of the inland vessel. These dimensions are determined by the CEMT classes (ranging from II to VI^{[2][2]}). In the model the CEMT classes are taken into account for the different OD relations. The total transport time for unimodal barge transport can be calculated with formula 8.

$$T_{UM_IWT} = T_{IWT} + T_{Handling} \quad (8)$$

The IWT transport time (T_{IWT}) is determined by the sailed distance (D_{IWT}) and the speed (V_{IWT}) of the inland vessel.

$$T_{IWT} = \frac{D_{IWT}}{V_{IWT}} \quad (9)$$

The total out-of-pocket cost for IWT transport will be calculated with formula 10.

$$\begin{aligned} (D_{IWT} < 1000 \rightarrow C_{IWT}(CEMT) = & \\ \frac{HC_{Sailing} \cdot T_{IWT_{Sailing}} + KC_{Sailing} \cdot D_{Sailing} + HC_{Waiting} + T_{IWT_{Waiting}}}{OCC_{IWT} \cdot Cap_{IWT} \cdot CF_{IWT}} \cdot (1 + P_{IWT_VAR_i}) \wedge & \\ (D_{IWT} > 1000 \rightarrow C_{IWT}(CEMT) = & \\ \frac{(HC_{Sailing} + HC_{Sailing_empty}) \cdot T_{IWT_{Sailing}} + (KC_{Sailing} + KC_{Sailing_empty}) \cdot D_{Sailing} + HC_{Waiting} + T_{IWT_{Waiting}}}{OCC_{IWT} \cdot Cap_{IWT} \cdot CF_{IWT}} \cdot (1 + P_{IWT_VAR_i}) & \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

In which

$HC_{SAILING}$ is the cost for sailing one hour for IWT vessel of a certain CEMT level [EUR/h]

$HC_{WAITING}$ is the cost per hour for an IWT vessel that is waiting [EUR/h]

$HC_{SAILING_EMPTY}$ is the hour cost for a vessel sailing in empty condition [EUR/h]

$KC_{sailing}$ and $KC_{Sailing_empty}$ are the kilometre cost for a fully loaded and empty barge

$P_{IWT_VAR_i}$ is the add-on for the different IWT cost elements dependent on a future scenario for commodity type i [%]

OCC_{IWT} is the occupancy rate of an inland vessel

CAP_{IWT} is the load capacity of an IWT vessel

CF_{IWT} is the correction factor for the occupation rate of inland vessels for transport flows in the same region. A correction factor of 50% is applied.

The total out-of-pocket cost depends on the sailed distance. If the transport distance is over 1,000 kms, it is assumed that there is no return cargo, while for short distances there is a higher probability of return cargo (especially for container transport).

Maritime transport

For maritime cargo flows, the same cost structure is used as in the case of rail transport (formula 11).

$$GC_{IM_IWT_M} = C_{IWT}(CEMT) + C_{Handling_IWT} + C_{road,PH} + T_{IM_IWT_M} \cdot VoT \quad (11)$$

The total intermodal IWT transport time for maritime flows ($T_{IM_IWT_M}$) can be calculated by using formula 12.

$$T_I M_I W T_M = (T_{IWT} + T_{Wait} + T_{handling-IW} + T_{Dwell} \cdot 24) \cdot (1 + VAR) + T_{PostHRoad} \quad (12)$$

Continental transport

Also for continual transport, the same cost structure is used as in the case of rail transport (formula 13).

$$GC_{IM_IWT_C} = C_{IWT}(CEMT) + 2 \cdot C_{Handling_IWT} + C_{road,PostH} + C_{road,PreH} + T_{IM_IWT_C} \cdot VoT \quad (13)$$

The same goes for the total transport time of IWT continental transport.

$$T_I M_I W T_M = (T_{IWT} + T_{Wait} + 2 \cdot T_{handling-IWT} + 2 \cdot T_{Dwell} \cdot 24) \cdot (1 + VAR) + T_{PostHRoad} \quad (14)$$

Annex II: Questionnaire Digital Twins

Questionnaire WP4 Deliverable 4.3.1. – Cost-benefit analysis (DTs)

For deliverable 4.3 it is necessary to quantify the main costs and benefits of the potential implementation of the developed CRISTAL technologies to create new business models. For this it is necessary to gather information via the questions below. Please provide detailed answers and quantify where possible (estimates are also ok). If the costs or benefits will be made/achieved in different years, please indicate when (e.g., y1, y2, y3). If it is not possible to answer a question at this moment, please indicate this. I understand that some of these questions will be difficult to answer, I still would like to ask them just in case you do have this information.

If there are specific costs or benefits concerning 1 or more of the 3 DTs, please specify this.

Costs

- a. What are the primary costs associated with the research and development of the DTs? (e.g., personnel, technology, prototyping)

Primary costs are personnel cost and the prototyping. In general, around EUR 414,457 is incurred for the creation of the prototype over the entire project period.

- b. Can you provide a breakdown of expenses, indicating major cost areas and investments for the development of the DTs?

We can't provide a precise breakdown, but the majority of costs related to personnel. Secondly, it's the prototyping.

- c. The DTs will use other technologies as data sources (both from CRISTAL and external sources). What are the costs related to this integration?

- a. **Fibre Optic Sensors:** - only personnel costs depending on the provided data.
- b. **Subsurface Inspection Radar:** - only personnel costs depending on the provided data.
- c. **Acoustic Emission:** - only personnel costs depending on the provided data.

- d. **Smart Buoys System:** - only personnel costs depending on the provided data.
- e. **External sources (e.g., AIPo, EURIS):** - only personnel costs depending on the provided data.

No additional costs for the integration of data are planned. Only openly available data is used.

- d. Are there any patents or intellectual property rights related to the technologies used in the DTs?

We only used open-source data/products. We will publish the DTs results as open source as well.

- e. Can the system integrate with existing transport management systems or resource planning systems? If yes, what are the costs related to data transmission? (This is important to know if there will be costs related to data transmission or integration in other systems)

Technically this is no problem, but as part of this research project this is not planned. No costs can be determined at the moment. In general, no costs for data transmission – only personnel costs for the setup of a publish subscribe system for alerts.

- f. Do DTs support APIs for seamless integration with other software applications?

No, only for the publish subscribe system for alerts.

- g. What is the initial setup cost for implementing the DTs somewhere? (e.g., on a pilot site or for other future users)

Not determinable as part of this research project

- h. Will there be ongoing maintenance or subscription fees? If yes, please provide details and quantification where possible.

Not determinable as part of this research project

We do not host this after publishing it – it is available as freely accessible software.

- i. Will there be a dedicated customer support team to assist clients?

No

- j. What will be the security costs for the production of the system?

No, keycloak is open source.

- k. Will there be energy consumption costs?

There are costs for users and developers (e.g. use of computers, etc.) but this is not determinable and part of the daily use. Nothing in particular has to be mentioned here.

- l. Will there be an environmental impact caused by the new technology? (e.g., raw materials, energy consumption, disposal)

Not determinable – impact is very low – only a prototype and software.

- m. Will there be other ongoing costs after the production of the DTs? (e.g., management team, security team, marketing, maintenance)

Not as part of the research phase – once the CRISTAL is done - there will be a prototype not a fully functional product for end customers!

2. Benefits

1. In what ways does your system help improve the resilience of the transport network?
 - a. Real time monitoring and analysis
 - b. Predictive maintenance
 - c. Traffic management
 - d. Resource allocation
 - e. Data driven decision making.
2. Can you provide specific examples of time and resource savings achievable by DTs?

In our pilots time will be saved for example for unnecessary waiting times due to failures of the locks. Additionally, different stakeholders have the opportunity to allocate their resources (ships and personnel) based on the water levels.

3. What will be the revenue model of the DTs? (Will it be a subscription fee, a onetime purchase...)

Not as part of the research phase – once the CRISTAL is done - there will be a prototype not a fully functional product for end customers!

4. What is the projected revenue stream over a specific time period? (1-year, 5-year, 10-year)

See answer to 2c.

5. What will/can be other sources of revenue for the DTs?

See answer to 2c.

6. Does your system help in identifying and mitigating risks in the supply chain, such as delays, disruptions, or inventory shortages?

Yes, as it provides insights on water levels, maintenance of locks or sediment displacements.

7. What long-term benefits do you anticipate businesses will gain from the continued use of your DTs?
 - a. Lower waiting times in front of locks due to maintenance
 - b. Early shifting of cargo possible to different modes of transport, once water levels are known (droughts, etc.)
 - c. Tracking data for a long time allows long term analyses and predictions for businesses.
8. Are there any plans for ongoing support and updates to ensure clients continue to experience benefits in the future?

Not part of the research project.

9. Does your system assist businesses in adhering to transportation regulations and compliance standards?

No, no focus of the DTs.

10. Will the system have positive effects on reducing the environmental footprint of transportation activities?

Certainly, by minimizing delays and helping to optimize transport routes. The SCMS has more impact here.

11. How does the implementation of your digital twins enhance customer satisfaction for businesses involved in the supply chain?

The transport chains of the pilot areas become more transparent and thus minimize potential failures or delays along these transport chains.

Annex III : Questionnaire SCMS

Questionnaire WP4 Deliverable 4.3.1. – Cost-benefit analysis (SCMS)

To complete deliverable 4.3, it is crucial to assess the main costs and benefits associated with implementing CRISTAL technologies for creating new business models. To gather this information, please respond to the following questions in detail. Whenever possible, provide quantitative data (estimations are acceptable). If costs or benefits occur in different years, specify the respective years (e.g., y1, y2, y3). If you cannot answer a question at the moment, please indicate so. I understand that some of these questions might be challenging, but I still appreciate your attempt to provide the information.

Costs

- a. What are the primary costs associated with the research and development of SCMS? (e.g., personnel, technology, prototyping)

The primary cost categories for the SCMS can be summarized to the following.

- *Staff (personnel) cost for the system development*
- *Staff (personnel) cost for system maintenance & operation*
- *(possible) Cost for connection to external platforms for acquiring necessary data.*
- *Cost for the promotion of the platform*
- *Cost for the scientific dissemination (papers, conferences)*
- *(possible) Cost for external hosting services for the platform or equipment/software for in-house hosting (During the duration of the project and the development of the prototype for testing the platform will be hosted inhouse therefore no additional cost is foreseen other than the personnel cost. In the later commercial exploitation phase and depending on the expected traffic/use of the platform, the cloud hosting of the platform may be required. However, the cost can only be defined then, depending on the specific hosting requirements that will emerge and choices that will be made.)*

- b. Can you provide a breakdown of expenses, indicating major cost areas and investments for the development of SCMS?

Specific amounts cannot be calculated at this stage, however, a rough qualitative estimation of the breakdown of annual expenses indicates that the major cost areas in

the future will be the personnel costs for maintaining, operating & updating (or expanding) the system, as well as the cloud hosting services if the platform is moved to an external provider of hosting services.

- c. The SCMS will use other technologies for data (both from CRISTAL and from external sources). What are the costs related to this integration?
- i. Fibre Optic Sensors Technology: *No additional cost is foreseen other than personnel costs, the input related to this technology will come through the Digital Twin.*
 - ii. Smart Buoys System: *No additional cost is foreseen other than personnel costs, the input related to this technology will come through the Digital Twin.*
 - iii. Acoustic Emission Technology: *No additional cost is foreseen other than personnel costs, the input related to this technology will come through the Digital Twin.*
 - iv. Digital Twin: *During the project duration no additional cost is foreseen. Later, it is depending on the relevant BM of the DTs and how it will offer its input to the SCMS.*
 - v. External sources (e.g., TMS, PMS, LSPs, GIS, Custom Systems and Financial Systems): *A decision for connection(s) to external platforms that require a fee for their services (e.g. a platform that provides visibility to rail/road services) is pending and will be decided during the development of the platform.*
- d. Are there any patents or intellectual property rights related to the technologies used in the SCMS?

No

- e. Can the system integrate with existing transport management systems or resource planning systems? If yes, what are the costs related to data transmission? (This is important to know if there will be costs related to data transmission or integration in other systems)

This answer is not available yet. However, if it will be decided for the SCMS to be able to transmit data to other systems, the cost will mainly include the development of the APIs required.

- f. Follow up: Does SCMS support APIs for seamless integration with other software applications?

Yes, it is planned to include APIs for this purpose.

- g. What is the initial setup cost for implementing SCMS somewhere? (e.g., on a pilot site or for future users)

The costs for implementing the SCMS on a site (e.g. for a future user) mainly include the personnel costs for setting up the system and connecting the available data sources to the platform (considering that the development of the SCMS core functionalities is completed). Moreover, as mentioned in 1a, there will be possibly additional costs for equipment or hosting of the SCMS if this will be done outside CERTH. In the case of the project pilots (e.g. the Italian pilot), no additional costs are foreseen since the pilot implementation is part of the overall SCMS development and the hosting for the prototyping will be done inhouse.

- h. Will there be ongoing maintenance or subscription fees? If yes, please provide details and quantification where possible.

Yes, during the commercial exploitation of the platform a fee will be required for the maintenance and further development of the system. However, details of the type of fees and the specific amounts are not yet calculated.

i. Will there be a dedicated customer support team to assist clients?

This answer is not available yet.

j. What will be the security costs to produce the system?

This answer is not available yet.

k. Will there be energy consumption costs?

Yes, but depending on the location of the hosting of SCMS, the energy consumption cost may be included in the external hosting services fees (paid by SCMS to the provider) or may be included in the SCMS services fee if the hosting of the platform will be in-house.

l. Will there be an environmental impact caused by the new technology? (e.g., raw materials, energy consumption, disposal)

No increased impacts to the environment by the operation of the SCMS are foreseen.

m. Will there be other ongoing costs after the production of SCMS? (e.g., management team, security team, marketing, maintenance)

Yes, most of the primary costs that are listed in question 1a (staff costs for system maintenance, operation (including also administrative staff) and further development, cost for the promotion of the platform and cost for hosting services), will continue to exist after the SCMS production.

Benefits

a. In what ways does your system help improve the resilience of the transport network?

SCMS contributes towards the resilience of the transportation network by providing to stakeholders increased visibility and awareness of the current and forecasted navigability status of the waterways, thus supporting (and proposing) well informed decisions for the cargo route planning (or re-planning), also utilizing the knowledge of the connections of IWW to the other land modes of transport (road/rail). In this way, SCMS aspires to secure the continuity of operations and therefore the resilience of the transportation network (from the operational point of view).

b. Can you provide specific examples of time and resource savings achievable by SCMS?

A short example of the efficiency achieved by the SCMS can be the following: A stakeholder interested in transporting his cargo through the river, inserts the details of his planned trip and requests to be informed for the status of the river navigability during the period of the transportation. The system compares the information included in the inventory of alerts (existing & forecasted) to the projected cargo movement and identifies the risks and points of disruption expected to hinder the transportation (if any). If a disruption is expected to stop the cargo from moving, based on the expected duration and the location of the disruption the system proposes feasible alternatives with the combination of inland navigation and rail (ideally) or road, or even the moving of cargo to another mode (e.g. perform the transport only by rail) to minimize the delay. The system also calculates the CO2 impact of these alternatives and informs the stakeholder. In addition, the system may update the information initially provided to the stakeholder if additional alerts occur until the time that the cargo will be loaded to the vessel to timely adjust the initial selection of route/mode and make a better use of the available resources.

c. What will be the revenue model of SCMS? (Will it be a subscription fee, a onetime purchase...)

This answer is not available yet.

- d. What is the projected revenue stream over a specific time period? (1-year, 5-year, 10-year)
This answer is not available yet.
- e. What will/can be other sources of revenue for SCMS?
Possible fee for using the SCMS APIs (by other platforms) in order to receive the output of the synchronodal route planning service (proposed alternatives) or to receive notifications from the inventory of alerts or the analytics from the SCMS observatory.
- f. Does your system help in identifying and mitigating risks in the supply chain, such as delays, disruptions, or inventory shortages?
The SCMS can help identify potential risks regarding delays and navigability disruptions through specific requests for routes along the river and can help mitigating them through providing visibility and proposing alternatives, engaging, when necessary, the other land modes of transport (road/rail).
- g. What long-term benefits do you anticipate businesses will gain from the continued use of your synchronodal corridor management system?
The main benefits include the following:
- *decrease of the total delays (& therefore costs) caused by IWW disruptions,*
 - *more reliable estimation of the time of arrival of cargo to its destination, therefore increased reliability for the businesses that are using the rivers compared to now,*
 - *better visibility of alternatives in cases of disruptions (with a focus on multimodality),*
 - *reduced cargo footprint while maintaining the same level of reliability of operations (by combining the modes, especially rail & IWW, instead of using trucks in cases of disruptions in the rivers, the operators can maintain their efficiency while not increasing their CO2 emissions)*
- h. Are there any plans for ongoing support and updates to ensure clients continue to experience benefits in the future?
Yes, the plan is to continue support and update the SCMS in the future, but the details are not defined yet.
- i. Does your system assist businesses in adhering to transportation regulations and compliance standards?
Not to the respondent's knowledge.
- Will the system have positive effects on reducing the environmental footprint of transportation activities?
Yes, because in cases of disruption and when there is a need to move to another mode of transport, the focus is first placed on promoting rail and not road which is the usual selection in such cases.
- j. How does the implementation of your synchronodal corridor management system enhance customer satisfaction for businesses involved in the supply chain?
Minimizing the degree of uncertainty regarding the navigability of rivers and the operational handling of disruptions will make businesses involved in the supply chain more reliable and flexible towards their customers' needs, therefore increasing the customers' level of satisfaction.

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